

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No. B420
 Date: 13 November 2008
 Take Off: 09:58:50
 Landing: 15:13:08
 Flight Time 5h 14m 08s

Campaign: VOCALS – 20 degrees South Flight 6

Operating Area: S.E. Pacific Ocean off the coast of northern Chile .

POB	Position	Name	Institute	Logs y/n
1	Captain	Luc Lathouwers	Directflight	
2	Co-pilot	Ian Ramsay Rae	Directflight	
3	CCM1	Dawn Quinn	Directflight	
4	Mission Scientist 1	Steve Abel	Met Office	
5	Flight Manager	Jim Crawford	FAAM	
6	Core Chem / AVAPS	Kate Turnbull	FAAM	
7	Cloud Physics	Martyn Pickering	Met Office	
8	SWS / SHIMS	Jeff Norwood-Brown	Met Office	
9	ARIES	Stuart Rogers	Met Office	
10	CAPS/2DS	Jonny Crosier	Manchester	
11	AMS / CCN	Paul Williams	Manchester	
12	Wet Neph / PSAP / Filters	James Bowles	Met Office	
13	CVI	Paul Barrett	Met Office	
14	CCN	Jamie Trembath	FAAM	
15				
16				
17				
18				
19				

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B420
 Date: 13 November 2008
 Project: VOCALS
 Location: Pacific off coast of northern Chile

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
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095218		GIN	0.16 kft	019	on
095423		ASP	0.17 kft	089	open
095850		T/O	0.14 kft	198	Arica
095850	100425	Profile 1	0.36 - 6.0 kft	199	
100426	101106	Run 1	6.0 kft	225	
100443		qnh	6.0 kft	225	1012
100507		nev	6.0 kft	225	zero
100542		jw	6.0 kft	226	zero
100558		heimann	6.0 kft	226	cal10
100955		bbr	6.0 kft	226	retract
101107	101701	Profile 2	6.0 - 0.49 kft	226	
101348		!	3.5 kft	224	ct 3820 radar
101427		!	2.8 kft	225	cb 3100 radar
101702	102204	Run 2	0.49 - 0.45 kft	222	
101917		jw	0.45 kft	224	zero
102204	102451	Profile 3	0.45 - 3.3 kft	224	
102452	103539	Run 3	3.3 - 3.4 kft	226	
102537		r3	3.3 kft	225	start
102614		r3	3.4 kft	225	3400ft
102647		qnh	3.4 kft	225	1015
103355		!	3.4 kft	228	point alpha
103539	103704	Profile 4	3.4 - 4.6 kft	269	
103614		!	3.9 kft	275	ct 3700ft
103704	104237	Profile 5	4.6 - 0.03 kft	273	
104237	104512	Profile 6	0.03 - 2.4 kft	269	
104513	105518	Run 4.1	2.4 - 2.3 kft	267	
104541		qnh	2.4 kft	269	1016
104558		r4.1	2.4 kft	271	2400ft
104709		JW	2.4 kft	268	zero check
104722		nev	2.3 kft	268	zero check
105518	105635	Profile 7	2.3 - 3.4 kft	270	
105635	110637	Run 4.2	3.4 - 3.5 kft	269	
110638	110844	Profile 8	3.5 - 5.4 kft	269	
110844	111515	Profile 9	5.4 - 0.03 kft	270	50ft
110900		heimann	5.2 kft	270	cal06
111001		!	4.2 kft	270	ct 4500
111153		!	2.4 kft	270	cb 2500
111515	111724	Profile 10	0.03 - 1.9 kft	269	50ft
111725	112724	Run 5.1	1.9 kft	271	
111754		qnh	2.0 kft	271	1016
111807		r5.1	2.0 kft	271	2000ft
112724	112801	Profile 11	1.9 - 2.4 kft	269	
112801	113301	Run 5.2	2.4 kft	270	
112844		r5.2	2.4 kft	271	2500ft
113302	113445	Profile 12	2.4 - 3.9 kft	268	
113445	114446	Run 5.3	3.9 - 3.8 kft	270	
113725		r5.3	3.8 kft	269	3900ft
113816		heimann	3.9 kft	269	cal 10
114446	114601	Profile 13	3.8 - 4.8 kft	267	
114602	115153	Profile 14	4.8 - 0.03 kft	269	
114712		jw	3.6 kft	268	zero set
114723		nev	3.5 kft	268	zero checked
115005		jw	1.00 kft	268	zero
115013		nev	0.88 kft	268	zero
115154	115224	Profile 15	0.01 - 0.38 kft	269	
115225	120351	Run 6.1	0.38 - 0.44 kft	267	
120220		r6.1	0.44 kft	268	500ft
120351	120649	Profile 16	0.44 - 3.4 kft	267	
120649	121951	Run 6.2	3.4 - 2.9 kft	267	
120918		r6.2	2.9 kft	268	3500 > 3000ft to stay in cloud

121951	122208	Profile 17	2.9 - 4.8 kft	267
122208	122748	Profile 18	4.8 - 0.00 kft	268 50ft
122749	122825	Profile 19	0.00 - 0.33 kft	269 50ft
122825	124010	Run 7.1	0.33 - 0.43 kft	268
122932		r7.1	0.40 kft	270 500ft
124010	124304	Profile 20	0.43 - 3.3 kft	264
124304	125307	Run 7.2	3.3 kft	268
124347		r7.2	3.4 kft	269 3500 radar, in cloud run
125307	125755	Profile 21	3.3 - -.03 kft	267 50ft
125611		JW	0.74 kft	079 zero
125621		nev	0.64 kft	083 zero
125756	131650	Profile 22	-.03 - 23.0 kft	085 50ft
131301		Sonde 1	17.9 kft	093
131651	144238	Run 8	23.0 kft	091
132147		Sonde 2	23.0 kft	090
133200		Sonde 3	23.0 kft	091
134214		Sonde 4	23.0 kft	090
134953		heimann	23.0 kft	092 cal06
135307		Sonde 5	23.0 kft	091
140415		Sonde 6	23.0 kft	091
141514		Sonde 7	23.0 kft	091
141953		Sonde 8	23.0 kft	090
142606		Sonde 9	23.0 kft	090
143651		Sonde 10	23.0 kft	089
144239	151308	Profile 23	23.0 - 0.16 kft	044
150241		P23	5.0 kft	046 interrupt
151308		Land	0.16 kft	184 as end p23
151405		ASP	0.17 kft	149 closed

B420 Track 13-NOV-08

FAAM Sortie, Flight B420
Thursday 12th November 2008
VOCALS Flight B420 – 20 S Cross-section

T/O **0700 local (1000 UTC)**
Land **1200 local (1500 UTC)**

Mission Scientists: Hugh Coe, Steve Abel

Operating Area: South East Pacific Ocean, off the west coast of northern Chile, along latitude line 20S

Waypoints:

ALPHA: 72°W 20°S

BETA: 80°W 20°S

Sortie Objectives: To sample aerosol and Sc cloud as a function of distance from the coast to the pristine background and to inter-compare cloud instruments with the 146.

Weather: High pressure system off shore capping a marine boundary layer with widespread Sc cloud. Near shore marine boundary layer winds from SSW.

Information:

Latest satellite image will be inserted prior to take-off

Flight patterns:

1. Take off and profile ascent 1000 ft/min immediately to 6,000 ft amsl to check instrumentation [12 min; T=0h 12 min]
2. Continue to point ALPHA, beginning cycle below starting with immediate profile descent to 50ft. [25 min; T=0h 37 min]
3. Perform cycle consisting of
 - a. profile descent to 50ft amsl,
 - b. climb to 500ft below cloudbase,
 - c. 10-min straight/level leg,
 - d. climb to 500ft below cloud top,
 - e. 10-min straight/level leg,
 - f. profile ascent to 1000ft above cloud top.
 - g. Possibly include a cloud top run
4. At point ALPHA turn to westerly heading and continue profile cycle above.
5. Repeat item 3 until arrival at point BETA or furthest west fuel allows. [2h 08min; T=2h 45m]
6. Turn onto reciprocal heading, descend to 50ft and immediately conduct a profile ascent to FL230 at 1000 ft/min [30m; T=3h 15m]
7. Continue en route returning to ALPHA at FL230, dropping sondes every 1 degree in longitude travelled. No sondes to be dropped between point ALPHA and Arica on return. [1h 28m; T=4h 43m]
8. Continue from point ALPHA to Arica at FL230 as far as possible until approach into Arica and land [37 m; T=5h20m]

Key Instrument Details:

SWS – as per instructions.

ARIES – as per instructions

CVI - During high level operate in aerosol mode with CVI hygrometer operating.

CVI – during in cloud runs operate in counterflow mode

Wet Neph – operated during all of 500ft runs

Dropsondes – 1 per degree of longitude on high level return between BETA and ALPHA

AMS – operate from Rosemount during aerosol and high level runs and profiles; operate on CVI during in cloud runs

Miss Scientist Notes:

VOCALS Flight B420 Summary
20 S Cross section including POC feature
Thursday 13th November 2008

T/O **0659 local (0959 UTC)**
Land **1213 local (1513 UTC)**

Mission Scientist: Steve Abel

Operating Area: South East Pacific Ocean, off the west coast of northern Chile, along a latitude line of 20S

Waypoints:

ALPHA: 72°W 20°S

BETA: 81°W 20°S

Sortie Objectives: To sample changes in the aerosol and Sc cloud as a function of distance along 20S away from the coastal region. Return at high level for radiation measurements and dropping sondes. Also to inter-compare cloud and aerosol instruments with the Do-228.

Weather: High pressure system off shore capping a marine boundary layer with widespread Sc cloud. Near shore marine boundary layer winds from SSW.

Cloud conditions: Visible GOES-10 imagery at 12:15 UTC (09:15 local) showing POC region on the 20S line and BAe146 flight track overlaid in green.

Mission Profile:

1. Take off and profile ascent immediately to 6,000 ft amsl followed by a profile descent to 500 ft amsl heading towards point ALPHA. Cloud tops variable. A 5 min 500' sub-cloud leg was then performed for intercomparison with the Do-228 which trailed the BAe-146. Light surface winds with no white-capping observed. AMS reported 8ug m⁻³ sulphate, CCN 200cc⁻¹, CPC 600 cc⁻¹ at start of run and gradually dropped off as moved away from coast.
2. 10 minute in cloud leg with Do-228 trailing for intercomparison. The cloud was thin with a base ~2900' and top ~3600'. FSSP 500 cc⁻¹, MVD 11um; CAS 500cc⁻¹, MVD 10um; CDP 300 cc⁻¹, MVD 11um. LWC was ~ 0.1 gm⁻³ and variable along run. Reached point ALPHA along this run and turned to head along the 20S line.
3. Profile ascent to 1000' above cloud top and immediate descent to 50' showed a well mixed BL.
4. 10 minute run at 2400' - approx 500' below cloud base. AMS reported ~ 1.5ug m⁻³ sulphate. No drizzle.
5. 10 minute in cloud run at 3500'. Little drizzle evident (max of 5L-1 with up to 150um drops on 2DC). CCN 100cc⁻¹, CPC 500cc⁻¹ and constant along run. FSSP 400-500 cc⁻¹, MVD 13um; CAS 450-500cc⁻¹, MVD 14um; CDP 220-300 cc⁻¹, MVD 13-14um.
6. As item 3. Cloud top now 4500' and base 2500'. Cloud thickening as go to West. Very clean above the BL. CCN 0 cc⁻¹ (S=1%), nephelometer showed scattering coefficients of 0, CPC 300 cc⁻¹. Below cloud CCN 150 cc⁻¹, CPC 635 cc⁻¹.
7. 10 minute sub-cloud run at 2000'. Along this run the cloud base was very variable. We were sometimes only ~100' below cloud base (small Cu rising into Sc). Followed by a 5 min run at 2500' at the altitude of the Cu but below the main Sc deck. 2DC and 2DS noting higher drizzle along these runs. CCN and CPC gradually dropping off as drizzle increases.
8. 10 minute in cloud run at 3900'. Cloud droplet conc decreased and MVD increased from previous cloud leg. FSSP 250 cc⁻¹, MVD 22um; CDP 190 cc⁻¹, MVD 20um. Towards the end of the leg popping in and out of cloud top (approx 4000').
9. As item 3. Elevated O₃ and CO above cloud but very little aerosol with CCN 0 cc⁻¹. Profile showed a decoupled BL. Lots of small Cu below the Sc deck.
10. 10 minute sub-cloud run at 500'. Very little aerosol CCN 25 cc⁻¹, CPC 180 cc⁻¹. 2DC and 2DS reporting heavier drizzle. Low sulphate on AMS. Clear gaps in the cloud – POC type region.

11. 10 minute in cloud run initiated at 3500'. FSSP 25 cc-1, MVD 40um; CDP 20 cc-1, MVD 40um, LWC 0.4 gm-3. Cloud top very variable and so continued run at 3000'. At times cloud thickness only ~ 500' and popped in and out of clear patches.

12. As item 3. Elevated O3 and CO above cloud but very little aerosol with CCN 0 cc-1. Profile showed a decoupled BL. Inversion at 980 mbar and several smaller ones above in sub-cloud layer. Lots of small Cu below the Sc deck. Rainbow observed.

13. 10 minute sub-cloud run at 500'. Sea surface has some white capping. Very little aerosol CCN 25 cc-1, CPC 80 cc-1. 2DC and 2DS reporting drizzle and appears heavy on windscreen at times. Very low sulphate concs on AMS – some of the lowest observed during VOCALS on the BAe146.

14. 10 minute in cloud run at 3400'. FSSP 40 cc-1, MVD 27um; CDP 20 cc-1, MVD 30um, 2DC reports drizzle drops up to 800um, 2D-S 250-300 um.

15. Profile descent to 50' at point BETA followed by a profile ascent to FL230 heading towards point ALPHA. Sub-cloud layer as observed in item 12. Elevated O3 and CO in a layer above cloud top (1500-2500m). CO peak about 75 ppb cf 55 ppb in BL and O3 peaked at 35 ppb cf 25 ppb in BL. No aerosol associated with this layer suggesting an aged air mass.

16. 10 sondes dropped along 20S line from 79W to 72W. 2 or 3 sondes in POC region.

Summary: An excellent 20S mission. BL deepened from point ALPHA along the 20S line until the POC region (see satellite imagery above.) Several legs below and in cloud within the POC were performed in combination with profiles. There were much lower cloud droplet concentrations and higher droplet MVD, larger drizzle rates and lower aerosol concentrations in the POC than in the thicker and more overcast Sc measured to the East of the POC (similar to previous POC missions). The BL was clearly decoupled in the POC region with small Cu rising into the main Sc. A series of sondes were dropped on the return leg with both the C-130 and Do228 passing beneath. The C-130 then sampled the POC after the BAe146 – a good joint mission. The Do228 intercomparison at the start of the flight also went well.

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B420 Date 13/11/08 Name STEVE ABEL Page 1 of 10

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
095957	T10	CP19 to	6000'		Clear skies above Africa. Do 228 going to take off strongly ^{immediately} after w/r
				18.42'S 70.36'W	Cloud starts
					5000' CO ~ 72ppb → instrument check
101107	P2↓	descent to	500'		variable cloud top evident in desert
					Cloud top 3700' LWC ~ 0.2gm ⁻³
					Cloud base 2900'
					Very hazy below cloud.
					Sea calm → no white capping
101702	R2	500'			AMS ~ 8µgm ⁻³ sulphate
					CCN @ 150/1500 above cloud
					200/600 below cloud.
					S = 0.1%
					CCN & sulphate dropping as go
					Ustr @ 150/1670 at end of run
					O ₂ increased 12 → 22ppb
102204	P3↑				Cloud base ~ 2900'
					Cloud very thin tops ~ 3600'
102537	R3	3400'			Cloud LWC ~ 0.15gm ⁻³
					Variable can see sea surface occasionally.
					CDP ~ 300cc ⁻¹ MWD 19µm
					FSSP 500cc ⁻¹ MWD ~ 11µm
					Small 75µm ~ 1-2L ⁻¹ on 20-C
					CAS ~ 500cc ⁻¹ MWD ~ 10µm

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B420 Date 13/11/08 Name STEVE ABEL Page 2 of 10

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
103203					g small gap in cloud - cloud very thin. LWC ~ 0.7 gm ⁻³ jumped up straight after gap. MWD increased to ~ 15µm. Cloud still very thin. Occasionally popping out of cloud top. So perhaps just near cloud top.
103539	PG↑	up to 4700'			Cloud top 3700'
103704	PS↓	to 50'			Cloud top 3700' Cloud base 29100'
					Sea state very calm → no whitecaps Profile looks fairly well mixed. CCN 50/400 below cloud base increased to ~ 100 cc ⁻³ mid way through profile and then back down near surface AMS → below ~ 2000' neph + AMS show fairly constant values. O ₃ ~ 10 ⁻⁷
104237	PG↑	up to 2400'			
104558	R4:1	~ 500' below cloud base			No drizzle on cloud physics SWS keeps falling over. CO ~ 65 ppb, O ₃ 25 ppb CCN 100/500 constant along run CO gradually increasing by ~ 5 ppb along run

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B.420 Date 13.11.08... Name STEVE ABEL Page 3 of 10

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
					AMS ~ 1.5 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$
105518	P7↑	to 3500'			Cloud base ~ 3000'
105635	R4.7	3500'			LWC ~ 0.15 g m^{-3}
					COP ~ 220 cc^{-1} MVD ~ 13-14 μm
					FSSP ~ 400 cc^{-1} MVD ~ 13 μm
					2D-C ~ 5L' 150 μm drop
					CAS ~ 450 - 500 cc^{-1} 14 μm
					not much drizzle or 2DS
					LWC fairly constant along run.
					COP 220 → 300 cc^{-1} along run.
					FSSP 400 → 550 cc^{-1} along run.
					110618 do see an increase in LWC.
110638	P8↑	to 5500'			Cloud top 4500' → cloud thickening as go to west
					Cloud tops very uniform, unlike near coast.
					neph size ~ 0 μm } above cloud
					CCN @ 1300 cc^{-1} } O ₃ looks like water injected above cloud → funny data
110866	P9↓	to 50'			Cloud top 4400'
					Cloud base 2500'
					LWC at top 0.5 g m^{-3}
					As each profile as go further west O ₃ increases. Profile well mixed again. Sea constant below cloud base ~ 12 μm

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B.629 Date 13/11/08 Name STEVE ABEL Page 4 of 10

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
					Sea state calm → no whitecaps
					Wind 6ms ⁻¹ @ 2000'
					CCN ~ 125 ¹⁵⁰ /625. bit higher than previous set of profiles to East. AMS also seeing slightly more sulphate. constant below cloud though
111725	RS1	2000'			ZDC and ZDS seeing some drizzle
093716					significant drop in cloud base. As for short time. Cloud base seems variable by ~ 500'. → poss small Cu rising into Sc
112206					Only ~ 100-200' below cloud. - Ando ZD-S seeing heavier drizzle.
112724	P117	6250'	RS2		Sum run still below ^{main} cloud but now in layer where we have small Cu and low rising into Sc ZDC ~ max duplet ~ 300µm
113233					Passed small Cu ~ 50' to our left. CCN 100/500 at start of run dropping to 75/400 towards end of run. Drizzle washing around out?

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B...420 Date 13/11/08 Name STEVE ABEL Page 5 of 10

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
113302	P121	to 3900'			LWC ~ 0.3 gm ⁻³
113445	RS-3	3900'			CDP ~ 190 cc ⁻¹ MVD ~ 22 μm FSSP ~ 250 cc ⁻¹ MVD ~ 20 μm 2D-C ~ 10 L ⁻¹ 200 μm max CAS ~ 600 cc ⁻¹ MVD ~ 20 μm ↑ coarse mode aerosol can account for some of this.
~113900					Flight deck cloud top at 3900' a small cloud core dropped off and MVD increased to 25 μm. corresponding increase to LWC.
116327					popping in and out of cloud top. → end of run got in and out of cloud top.
116446	PB1	to 5000'			Cloud top 4000'
116602	PK1	to 50'			CO and O ₃ increase above cloud top. Very little aerosol above cloud top can O ₃ ⁻¹ Some as seen on previous days Aged air mass above cloud top and very little aerosol Cloud base ~ 2800' but with variable small Cs below Profile much less well mixed → small Cs below Se

peak in neph ~ 1500' prob associated with moist layer in profile
O₃ ~ 10 μ⁻¹ below cloud & to 30 μ⁻¹ in moist layer - photo

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B.420 Date 13/11/08 Name STEVE ABEL Page 6 of 10.

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
					CCN saw spike as well AMS sulphate levels still decreasing
115124	P1S1				in general as move Westwards
115221	R6.1	500'			Low cloud bases at start of run so 10min leg at 500'
					Cloud base very variable.
					ZD-C and ZD-S reporting drizzle Aerosol very clean 1000cc^{-1}
					Low CO ₂ , low sulphate etc.
120042					CCN 25/180 CO ₂ ~ 60ppb.
					Looking to South some gaps in the cloud.
120351	P161	to 3500'			Main cloud base ~ 2600'
120649	R6.2	3500'			Cloud LWC ~ 0.4g m^{-3} CA ~ 150cc^{-1} MUD ~ 30- 40 µm ZD-S not much drizzle COP ~ 20cc^{-1} MUD = 40µm FSSP ~ 25cc^{-1} MUD = 40µm ZDC seeing ~ 1000L^{-1} ~ 20µm
120918					Had to drop to 3000' as came out of cloud top → very variable tops, clear patches. Quite near cloud base at times. LWC ~ 0.15g m^{-3}
121108					Out of cloud top. Cloud only ~ 500' thick.
121540					Back into cloud.

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B.420 Date 13/11/06 Name STEVE ABEY Page 7 of 10

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
					Much more drizzle. Cloud very thin - lower droplet concs. Larger MVD. Gaps in cloud. A lot aerosol below cloud. Almost like a POC ^{in terms of pds} interesting to look at sat pic after.
121951	P17↑				Cloud top ~ 3900'. Definite holes in the cloud. Neph conc = 0 CCN ~ 0 above cloud top. No aerosol.
122208	P18↓	to 50'			Cloud top 3800' Cloud base ~ 2600' but very variable Definite gaps in cloud on profile down through cloud base. Below cloud can see holes in Sc. Cu rising into Sc with drizzle. Rainbow. BL decoupled Inversion at ~ 900m and several smaller ones above that
122748	P19↑	to 500'			
122825	R7.1	500'			Sea or neph variable - 5-10m ⁻¹ CCN 25/80 - sulphate very low from AMS -20-C some drizzle along with neph spiking with drizzle. Wind speed ~ 7m ⁻¹ Small whitecaps

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B670 Date ...13/11/05 Name ...STEVE ABEL Page 8 of 10

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
					AMS → cleanest seen on a 205 mission
124010	P20↑	to 3600'			Lots of drizzle on wind sheet ^{screen} at 1100' 20C larger drops ~ 50µm max. Cloud base 2000'
124306	R7.2	3600'			COP 20cc ⁻¹ MVD 30µm FSSP 40cc ⁻¹ MVD 27µm 20-C drizzle 200L ⁻¹ 30µm max CAS 150cc ⁻¹ MVD 25µm 20-S drizzle up to 250-300µm
124730					20-C reports drizzle drops up to 80µm.
125038					^{small} Break in cloud → see the surface and small Cu below.
125307	P21↓	to 50'			Profile to 50' in turn. Max western extent 81°6' W. Drizzle on windshield. Gaps in cloud. Cu rising into E. 2 photos. Sea surface a few whitecaps. Wind 4-5ms ⁻¹
125756	P22↑	to FL230			Several inversions in sub-cloud layer Cloud top 3900' CN, CCN, neph very low above cloud but CO shatypb 7Spbh and O ₂ to 3Spbh.

c-b 58ppt and 25ppt below cloud

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B.470 Date 13/11/08 Name STEVE ABEL Page 9 of 10

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
131052					2 Photos taken of holes in cloud
131301					Sonde 1 20.0S 79.8W FL190
131500					2 photos taken → open regions look like have convective towers around boundary in places.
131651	R8	FL230			
132147					Sonde 2 20.0S 79.0W FL230
133200					Sonde 3 20.0S 78.0W FL230
133630					Boundary between SWcast & anal region with more "PCL" type mes is ~77.20W → c-f sat pic
134214					Sonde 4 20.0S 77.0W FL230 Just had look at sat-pic → definitely a POC feature that we suspect. Excellent flight!
135307					Sonde 5 20.0S 76.0W FL230
140415					Sonde 6 20.0S 75.0W FL230
141514					Sonde 7 20.0S 74.0W C-130 at 74:21W Sonde 7 - no winds ^{above} seen ^{travelling West low-level} Di-228 ^{passing} well
141953					Sonde 8 - 20.0S 73.6W
142606					Sonde 9 - 20.0S 73.0W

2

VOCALS BAe-146 Instrument status Report

Date of report(UTC): 2008/11/13 16:30

Author of report: Steve Abel

Submitted at(UTC): 2008/11/13 16:37

Remaining flight hours: 0

General Comments:

After 20S flight (B420)

INSTRUMENTS/SYSTEMS STATUS

= up;
 = provisional;
 = down ;
 = no report

Meteorology/Navigation

1.	GPS (Patch)	Comment:	
2.	GPS (Cruciform)	Comment:	
3.	Temperature/Pressure	Comment:	
4.	Water Vapor (Hygrometer)	Comment:	
5.	Turbulence Probe	Comment:	
6.	Altitude (RadarAlt)	Comment:	
7.	Doppler Radar	Comment:	
8.	Dropsonde (AVAPS)	Comment:	10 sondes launched - 1 had no wind data above 700mbar.

Radiation

9.	Broadband Radiometer (BBR)	Comment:	
10.	Spectral Radiometer (ARIES)	Comment:	
11.	In-flight Microwave Obs System (DEIMOS)	Comment:	
12.	Microwave Radiometer Scanning System (MARSS)	Comment:	not operated
13.	Shortwave Spectrometer (SWS)	Comment:	problems at start of flight.
14.	Spectral Irradiance (SHIM)	Comment:	lower SHIMS not working, upper ok
15.	Heimann Downward-facing Radiometer	Comment:	

Chemistry

16.	Ozone (CAMP 2B)	Comment:	
17.	NOx	Comment:	not operated on B420
18.	CO (AL5002)	Comment:	
19.	SO2 (TECO 43C)	Comment:	
20.	Sample Bottles (WAS)	Comment:	not carried in VOCALS
21.	CH4/CO2 (NIR-TDLAS)	Comment:	
22.	PAN (GC)	Comment:	not operated
23.	Volatile Aerosol Composition (VACC)	Comment:	
24.	CH4/N2O (1C-TDLAS)	Comment:	

Cloud Physics and Aerosol

25.	Liquid and Total water probe	Comment:	
26.	LWC (Johnson Williams)	Comment:	
27.	TWC	Comment:	
28.	FFSSP	Comment:	
29.	2D-C	Comment:	
30.	PCASP	Comment:	believed to still have leak - Ch2 counts substituted for Ch1 counts to generate spectrum/total concs, but concs still too high
31.	Small Ice Detector (SID-2)	Comment:	not fitted
32.	Cloud and Precipitation Imager (CIP-15)	Comment:	needs alignment
33.	Cloud Droplet Probe (CDP)	Comment:	
34.	Condensation Nucleus Counter (CNC)	Comment:	
35.	Cloud Condensation Nuclei Spectrometer (CCNc)	Comment:	only 1 channel working
36.	Fluorescence water vapour sensor (FWVS)	Comment:	
37.	Dry Nephelometer	Comment:	
38.	Wet Nephelometer	Comment:	
39.	Black Carbon (PSAP)	Comment:	
40.	Filters	Comment:	

41.	Aerosol Mass Spectrometer (AMS)	Comment:	
42.	Counter-flow virtual Impactor (CVI)	Comment:	
43.	2-D Imaging Probe (SPEC-2D-S-128H)	Comment:	
44.	CAPS	Comment:	
45.	Single Particle Soot Photometer (SP-2)	Comment:	not fitted
46.	Fine-mode Aerosol Spectrometer (UHSAS)	Comment:	not fitted
47.	Scanning Mobility Particle Sizer (SMPS)	Comment:	
48.	Ultrafine particle counter 1 (LP-WUCPC-1)	Comment:	
49.	Ultrafine particle counter 2 (LP-WUCPC-2)	Comment:	

Other

50.	SATCOM C	Comment:	
51.	SATCOM H	Comment:	
52.	Up, Down, Front, Rear Digital Imagery	Comment:	

[prev](#) | [next](#)

 [Back to VOCALS Field Catalog](#) | [edit](#) | [delete](#)

comments : gstoss at ucar.edu

Chemistry Log

Date: 13/11/08 Flight: B420 Operator: KT.

Preflight *CO, O₃, ~~NO_x~~, SO₂ operated.*

No. ? or x	Location	Action	Comments
Gases			
1	☒ CO2/Ar	Outlet pressure is between 2 2.5 bar	155
2	☒ CO2/Ar	Inlet pressure not less than 20 psi	
3	☒ CO standard	Outlet pressure is between 2 2.5 bar	
4	☒ CO standard	Inlet pressure not less than 20 psi, note pressure	35
5	☒ Nitrogen	Outlet pressure is between 2 2.5 bar	
6	☒ Nitrogen	Inlet pressure not less than 20 psi, note pressure	90
Flows			
7	☒ Ozone sample flows	Flow ~ 0.7 LPM on both channels	
8	☒ NOx sample flow	~ 1 LPM	
9	☒ NOx Ozonator flow	~ 0.065 LPM	
10	☒ CO lamp flow	~ 40 ml/min	
11	☒ CO cell pressure	~ 7.5 bar	
12	☒ CO Pressure monochromator	~ 5 bar	
Zeros			
13	☒ Ozone zero	Performed OK (if not approx zero note values)	
14	☒ NOx zero	Performed OK (if not approx zero note values)	
15	☒ CO zero	Left for approx 10 min	
Other			
16	☒ Tubing	All inlets / exhausts connected	
17	☒ HORACE data	Check data is being displayed and recorded	
18	☒ CO calibration	If unattended set to auto cal (40 min)	
TDLAS			
19	☒ 230V	230V power breakers on	
20	☒ 28V	Red LED on front panel (ensure LTI breaker on)	
21	☒ Laptop	On and software working	
22	☒ Data	Being saved to correct directories	

NOx Ozonator flow = 0 → Instrument switched off

Post Flight

Switch off			
1	☒ CO	Switch off instrument	
2	☒ Ozone	Switch off monitor	
3	☒ NOx	Switch off monitor	
4	☒ Pumps	Switch off all pumps	
5	☒ Breaker	Pop all breakers on rack and SSP	
Gases (note pressures)			
6	☒ CO2/Ar	Close valves and check inlet pressure not below 20 psi	155
7	☒ CO standard	Close valves and check inlet pressure not below 20 psi	40
8	☒ Nitrogen	Close valves and check inlet pressure not below 20 psi	85
If below 20 psi then the cylinder needs changing refilling			
Driers			
9	☒ Small drier	Change if spent	
10	☒ Large drier	Change if spent	
TDLAS			
11	☒ Data transfer	To memory stick	
12	☒ Laptop	Shut down	
13	☒ Switch off instrument	Pull all breakers IF no other instrument on	
Log			
14	☒ Flight Log	Put log in folder (notify Ruth of any issues)	
15	☒ Faults	Fill out separate log for in flight issues put in flight folder	
16	☒ TDLAS data	Send to project spaces on BADC	

*NOx requires attention!
- Ozonator flow = 0.*

Chemistry Log

In flight

CO calibrations only need carrying out when the lamp temperature changes, if unsure perform a quick cal first.

During each CO calibration check Ozone and NOx flows are similar to those observed pre-flight

Time	Flight level	CO				
		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgrd Count (Hz)	Lamp Temp (deg C)	Cell Pressure (Torr)
09:56	Taxy	94.63	296.56	28063	37.86	7.54
Time	Flight level	CO				
		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgrd Count (Hz)	Lamp Temp (deg C)	Cell Pressure (Torr)
Time	Flight level	CO				
		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgrd Count (Hz)	Lamp Temp (deg C)	Cell Pressure (Torr)

CO 'Cal'

Flight level	Zero Start	Zero End	Counts (Hz)	Span Start	Span End	Conc. Range	Counts range	Sensitivity	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgrd Count (Hz)	Pressure Cell (Torr)	Lamp Temp	O3 Intensities
2300FT	10:45	-5ppb	27800			512	76400				7.52	37.97	111 kHz
1900FT	11:18	-5ppb	27800			510	76400				7.52	37.87	111 kHz
3400FT	12:07	-3ppb	27600			511	76600				7.51	37.03	111 kHz
2300FT	13:20	-3ppb	27595			517	76907				7.31	37.04	110.825
2300FT	14:10	-7ppb	273±3			510	75944				7.26	39.02	1106.02
Taxy	15:13	-6ppb	27400			516	76200				7.51	38.93	110 kHz

Time	Flight level	CO				
		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgrd Count (Hz)	Lamp Temp (deg C)	Cell Pressure (Torr)

In flight comments

Sticky Cal value on CO?

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B 420

Date: 13/11/08	Operator: MAP	DRS Time: +0	DAU1 Time: +0	DAU2 Time: +0	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time: +0	Page 1 of 4
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		Manchester FSSP		CIP25			CDP			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Mean Dia	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Mean Dia	LWC		
																50 micron bead test CDP + FFSSP	
10:01:50	60	0.07	2													FL030	
10:02:31	50	0.07	2													FL040	
10:03:27	20	0.08														FL050	
10:05:36	10	0.08														End of Profile 1 & Start Run 1 @ FL060	
10:06:00	40	0.07															
10:08:00	40	0.07															
10:10:00	60	0.07															
10:11:12																End of Run 1 & Start Profile 2	
10:12:18	100	0.07														FL050	
10:13:20	60	0.07														FL040	
10:14:13	220	0.07	63													FL030	
10:15:10	260	0.07														FL020	
10:16:08	300	0.07														FL010	
10:17:01																End of P2 & Start Run 2 @ 500'	
10:18:00	200	0.07															
10:20:00	200	0.07															
10:22:01																End of Run & Start P3	
10:22:54	130	0.07														FL010	
10:23:47	80	0.07														FL020	
10:24:40	100	0.07														FL030	
10:25:07																End of P3	
10:25:43																Start Run 3 @ 3400'	
10:26:00	70	0.07	266			2	50	550	12			0.15	250	10	0.15	12	
10:28:00	20	0.10	514			1	75	600	11			0.15	350	11	0.2	12	
10:30:00	20	0.10	730			3	125	500	11			0.15	350	11	0.2	12	
10:32:00	20	0.09	930			7	100	400	14			0.30	200	15	0.3	12	
10:34:00	40	0.09	1137			5	100	400	13			0.3	200	14	0.25	12	
10:35:40																End of Run 3 & Start P3	
10:36:28	20	0.09	1340													FL040	
10:37:11																End of P3 & Start P4 @ 4500'	
10:37:40	25	0.07														FL040	
10:38:48	85	0.07	1377													FL030	
10:39:45	100	0.07														FL020	
10:40:45	110	0.07														FL010	
10:42:35	120	0.07														End of P & Start P5	
10:43:48	120	0.07														FL010	
10:45:12																End of P5 & Start Run 4.1 @ 2400'	
10:46:00	55	0.07															
10:48:00	80	0.07															
10:50:00	90	0.07	1378														
10:52:00	100	0.07															
10:54:00	70	0.07															

PCASP Reference Volts = 8V	FFSSP Reference Volts = 3.3V	2D2-C End element 1 voltage = -1.3V	CIP25 End element 1 voltage = 0.7V	CIP100 End element 1 voltage = n/a
PCASP Flow rate = 1.9CC/sec		2D2-C End element 32 voltage = -1.5V	CIP25 End element 64 voltage = 0.7V	CIP100 End element 64 voltage = n/a
© Met Office 2007	SID2 Laser power = n/a	2D2-P End element 1 voltage = n/a		

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B 420

Date: 13/11/08	Operator: MAP	DRS Time: +0	DAU1 Time: +0	DAU2 Time: +0	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time: +0	Page 2 of 4
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		Manchester FSSP		CIP25			CDP			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Mean Dia	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Mean Dia	LWC		
10:55:18																End of Run 4.1 & Start P7	
10:56:10	60	0.08														FL030	
10:56:30																End of P & Start Run 4.2 @ 3500'	
10:58:00	60	0.16	1702			4	175	450	13			0.3	210	13	0.3	12	
11:00:00	5	0.15	1936			3	200	430	14			0.35	220	14	0.35	1	
11:02:00	120	0.16	2230			1	200	450	14			0.35	220	14	0.3	1	
11:04:00	40	0.19	2570			2	150	600	14			0.3	300	13	0.3	1	
11:06:31																End of Run & Start P8	
11:07:08	100	0.18	3325			20	250	600	18			0.8	290	20	1	1	
11:08:43	10	0.07	3362													End of P & Start P9 @ FL055	
11:10:14	120	0.20	3505			15	225	550	17			0.7	220	17	0.6	1	
11:12:11	175	0.07	3739			1	250									FL020	
11:13:11	170	0.07														FL010	
11:15:15	160	0.07														End of P9 & Start P10 @ 50'	
11:16:29	100	0.07														FL010	
11:17:25																End of P & Start Run 5.1 @ 2000'	
11:18:00	90	0.07	3740			3	250									1	
11:20:00	110	0.07				5	300									1	
11:22:00	150	0.07				10	325									1	
11:24:00	80	0.07															
11:26:00	60	0.07				2	300										
11:27:24																End of Run & Start P11	
11:28:00																End of P11 & Start Run 5.2 @ 2500'	
11:29:00	60	0.08	3741			4	250									1	
11:31:00	80	0.07				3	300									1	
11:33:00																End of Run & Start P12	
11:34:40																End of P12 & Start Run 5.3 @ 2900'	
11:35:00	60	0.17	3901			35	300	260	19			0.6	190	20	0.8	1	
11:37:00	120	0.18	4166			30	150	230	19			0.6	180	22	0.8	1	
11:39:00			Fail														
11:41:00	110	0.11	25			100	150	160	24			1	110	24	1	1	
11:43:00	100	0.11	247			140	200	110	24			0.7	90	25	0.6	1	
11:44:48																End of Run & Start P13	
11:45:54	5	0.07														End of P13 & Start P14 @ 5000'	
11:46:45	15	0.07														FL040	
11:47:50	60	0.19	382			90	350								1	FL030	
11:48:55	20	0.07	384			10	400								1	FL020	
11:49:59	60	0.07														FL010	
11:51:52	45	0.07														End of P14 & Start P15 @ 50'	
11:52:25																End of P15 & Start Run 6.1 @ 500'	
11:53:00	20	0.07															
11:55:00	40	0.07															
11:57:00	30	0.07															

PCASP Reference Volts = 8V	FFSSP Reference Volts = 3.3V	2D2-C End element 1 voltage = -1.3V	CIP25 End element 1 voltage = 0.7V	CIP100 End element 1 voltage = n/a
PCASP Flow rate = 1.9CC/sec		2D2-C End element 32 voltage = -1.5V	CIP25 End element 64 voltage = 0.7V	CIP100 End element 64 voltage = n/a
© Met Office 2007	SID2 Laser power = n/a	2D2-P End element 1 voltage = n/a		

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B 420

Date: 13/11/08	Operator: MAP	DRS Time: +0	DAU1 Time: +0	DAU2 Time: +0	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time: +0	Page 3 of 4
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		Manchester FSSP		CIP25			CDP			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Mean Dia	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Mean Dia	LWC		
11:59:00	20	0.07	384														
12:01:00	10	0.07															
12:03:50																End of Run & Start P16	
12:05:23	10	0.08	385													FL020	
12:06:54																End of P & Start Run 6.2 @ 3500'	
12:07:00	130	0.20	407			2000	225	25	30			0.6	20	40	0.6	1	
12:11:00	45	0.21	477			230	250	40	30			0.3	25	25	0.2	1	
12:13:00	80	0.21	531			215	350	50	28			0.5	40	30	0.4	1	
12:15:00	45	0.21	575			200	200	20	25			0.25	20	35	0.2	1	
12:17:00	7	0.16	583			15	175									1	
12:19:50																End of Run & Start P17	
12:22:05	5	0.06														End of P17 & Start P18 @ 5000'	
12:22:54	5	0.06														FL040	
12:24:59	30	0.07	682			300	300	20	38			0.6	15	40	0.3	1	
12:24:57	15	0.07	684			5										FL030	
12:25:50	10	0.07														FL020	
12:27:49	8	0.07														FL010	
12:28:27																End of P18 & P19 @ 50'	
12:29:00	5	0.07	685													End of P19 & Start Run 7.1 @ 500'	
12:31:00	25	0.07															
12:33:00	35	0.07															
12:35:00	5	0.07															
12:37:00	5	0.07															
12:39:00	5	0.07	741			2	300									1	
12:40:12																End of Run & Start P20	
12:40:51	20	0.08	867			10	500									1	
12:41:46	20	0.06	872			60	500									1	
12:43:04																End of P & Start Run 7.2 @ 2900'	
12:44:00	40	0.21	900			275	250	16	25			0.25	20	30	0.2	1	
12:46:00	110	0.20	970			100	275	60	23			0.5	50	23	0.5	1	
12:48:00	100	0.19	1090			100	325	70	23			0.5	60	27	0.5	1	
12:50:00	15	0.20	1140			800	250	20	30			0.15	10	30	0.2	1	
12:53:09																End of Run & Start P21	
12:54:37	25	0.09	1247			15	200									1	
12:55:38	5	0.07														FL020	
12:57:53	10	0.07														FL010	
12:59:01	10	0.07				1	200									End of P & Start P22 @ 50'	
13:00:00	30	0.07														FL010	
13:00:57	50	0.16				20	300	60	22			0.55	60	25	0.6	1	
13:02:00	2	0.07														FL030	
13:03:03	5	0.07														FL040	
13:04:09	5	0.06														FL050	
13:05:09	5	0.06														FL060	
																FL070	

PCASP Reference Volts = 8V	FFSSP Reference Volts = 3.3V	2D2-C End element 1 voltage = -1.3V	CIP25 End element 1 voltage = 0.7V	CIP100 End element 1 voltage = n/a
PCASP Flow rate = 1.9CC/sec		2D2-C End element 32 voltage = -1.5V	CIP25 End element 64 voltage = 0.7V	CIP100 End element 64 voltage = n/a
© Met Office 2007	SID2 Laser power = n/a	2D2-P End element 1 voltage = n/a		

FAAM Dropsonde Flight Log

Flight No.	B420	Date	13/11/2008	Operator	KFT	Page No.	1 of 1
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GMT	Sonde No.	Event <i>eg land, splashdown</i>	Comments <i>pressure hPa, T deg C, RH %, wind direction deg, wind speed m/s, longitude, latitude, height m</i>
131303	1	Launch	505.70 -6.60 18.91 189.00 6.60 0.40 -79.833600 -19.999300 5490.70
132040	1	Splashdown	1013.95 16.07 75.98 145.01 4.30 -12.40 -79.843802 -19.990865 -282.07 Launched sensor end first. Parachute NOT repacked.
132154	2	Launch	409.50 -17.70 10.26 253.10 7.70 0.50 -78.987200 -19.993800 7018.90
133054	2	Splashdown	1014.24 15.25 87.97 105.58 2.78 -12.70 -79.002730 -19.977416 99999.00 Launched sensor end first. Parachute NOT repacked. Late launch detect.
133203	3	Launch	409.60 -17.70 10.70 246.50 6.90 0.40 -77.994400 -19.999900 7016.60
134112	3	Splashdown	1006.40 14.58 82.04 128.05 6.14 -12.12 -78.006661 -19.983231 -296.37 Launched sensor end first. Parachute NOT repacked.
134218	4	Launch	409.80 -17.30 11.61 256.10 6.60 0.50 -76.994500 -20.002400 7012.80
135119	4	Splashdown	1006.06 15.37 77.89 144.42 4.75 -11.77 -77.009502 -19.985454 -297.31 Launched sensor end first. Parachute NOT repacked.
135313	5	Launch	411.07 -6.34 3.52 0.00 0.00 0.00 -75.997620 -20.000471 7183.36
140207	5	Splashdown	1006.34 15.64 76.39 174.63 3.43 -12.37 -76.008830 -19.984950 -299.63 Launched sensor end first. Parachute repacked. Late launch detect.
140415	6	Launch	409.60 -17.20 6.98 261.50 5.40 0.70 -74.998500 -20.008400 7016.50
141332	6	Splashdown	1004.80 16.42 70.15 111.17 1.36 -11.55 -75.009652 -19.993063 -292.48 Launched sensor end first. Parachute NOT repacked.
141518	7	Launch	409.60 -16.90 9.29 262.90 6.90 0.60 -73.993500 -20.010700 7016.60
142424	7	Splashdown	1012.47 17.59 64.52 8.04 0.49 -10.46 -74.007052 -19.994535 99999.00 Launched sensor end first. Parachute NOT repacked.
141956	8	Launch	407.33 6.30 1.20 264.87 75.40 -11.20 -73.571601 -20.010398 7373.42
142913	8	Splashdown	1013.35 17.56 63.66 12.31 2.06 -8.64 -73.580162 -19.994574 99999.00 Launched sensor end first. Parachute NOT repacked. Late launch detect.
142609	9	Launch	409.70 -16.70 9.43 265.20 8.50 0.60 -72.996100 -20.008200 7015.30
143520	9	Splashdown	1005.71 16.74 64.52 72.74 0.33 -9.10 -73.006838 -19.991664 -295.04 Launched sensor end first. Parachute NOT repacked.
143657	10	Launch	409.80 -16.70 5.86 264.00 9.10 0.60 -71.991800 -19.997200 7014.10
144559	10	Splashdown	1012.52 17.46 66.62 247.76 1.86 -10.50 -72.003089 -19.983034 99999.00 Launched sensor end first. Parachute NOT repacked.
			All data transmitted to WMO.

size	#	charged	Flight/Date	discharged	Comment
10 1	2	KWS 12/11	B420 13/11		
10 1	3 4	KWS 12/11	B420 13/11		
10 1	7 8	KWS 12/11	B420 13/11		
10 1	10 69	KWS 12/11	B420 13/11		
10 1	21 23	KWS 12/11	B420 13/11		filter passed
10 1	33 40	KWS 12/11	B420 13/11		

B420

Flight:

B420

KEY

Not Fitted

Fitted, Not Operated

Duff Data

Minor Problem

OK

Thermometers

Cabin Temperature:

Heimann:

Deiced Temp:

Non-deiced Temp:

Hygrometers

FWVS:

Buck CR2:

General Eastern:

Johnson Williams:

Nezvorov:

Total Water Probe:

Cameras

Downward Facing:

Forward Facing:

Rearward Facing:

Upward Facing:

Navigation + Aircraft

Cruciform GPS:

GIN Applanix:

INU Honeywell:

Radar Altimeter:

RVSM IAS:

RVSM Static Pressure:

XR5 GPS:

Misc Core

HORACE:

AMTG:

AVAPS:

Cabin Pressure:

Printer:

S9 Static Pressure:

Satcom C:

Satcom H (VIRC):

Turb Centre-Static:

Turb Left Right:

Turb Up-Down:

Turb Horizontal Chk:

Turb Vertical Chk:

Weather Radar:

DLUs:

DLU AERACK:

DLU BBR Lower:

DLU BBR Upper:

DLU Core Chem:

DLU Core Consoles:

DLU Port Aft:

DLU Port Fwd:

DLU Stbd Fwd:

Radiometers

Lower:

BBR (clear) Lower:

BBR (IR) Lower:

BBR (red) Lower:

Upper:

BBR (clear) Upper:

BBR (IR) Upper:

BBR (red) Upper:

ARIES:

DEIMOS:

IR Camera:

JNO2 Lower:

JNO2 Upper:

JO1D Lower:

JO1D Upper:

MARSS:

SHIMS Lower:

SHIMS Upper:

SWS:

TAFTS:

Cloud Probes

2DC:

2DP:

FFSSP:

PCASP:

PCASP SPP-200:

2DS:

ADA:

CAPS:

CCN:

CDP (fuselage):

CDP (Canister):

CIP 100 (PIP):

CIP 25 (CIP):

CPI:

CVI (Inlet):

CVI PCASP-X:

CVI Ly-A Hygro:

FSSP (UMan):

SID1:

SID2:

SID3:

Aerosol

CPC 3025A:

CPC 3786 H2O:

Filters 47mm:

Filters 90mm:

Neph - Dry:

Neph - Wet:

PSAP:

AMS:

CPC (AMS):

SMPS (AMS):

CPC 3010A (CVI):

INC:

Mini-LIDAR:

SP2:

UHSAS:

VACC:

Chemistry

CO Aerolaser 5002:

NOx TE42C:

Ozone TE49C:

Ozone TE49:

SO2 TE43C:

TDLAS (NIR) CH4:

TDLAS (NIR) CO2:

FAGE:

Formaldehyde:

NOx FAAM:

NOxy:

ORAC:

PAN:

PERCA:

Peroxide:

PTRMS:

TDLAS (1C):

WAS Bags:

WAS Bottles:

Misc Non-Core

CASI/ATM:

LIDAR (big):

LTI:

SAW Hygrometer:

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B420

Date: 13/11/08

Issues

1. RFC/DFC bay – suspect water running down inside of RFC and DFC windows. Pictures ok
2. TWC – status flag occasionally flashing Status bit 4094.

Instruments

Dropsondes	10, 9 good, 1 very late winds
CVI -	ok
Filters	ok
Neph	ok
PSAP	ok
WetNeph	ok
AMS	ok
Core Chem	ok nox failed, co good
Cloud physics -	ok PCASP channel 1 noisy otherwise scale error (leak) Ok
ARIES -	ok
MARSS -	unserviceable
SWS -	intermitantly good, no lower shims
CCN	ok, single channel only.
VACC -	unserviceable
CPC	ok
PAN	ok
2DS -	ok
CAPS -	ok
SMPS -	ok
Buck -	experimental operation ->ok

Aircraft

SatcomC	ok
MPDS	Run for last part of flight, ok
ISDN Emails	Nil
Satcom-H Calls	Nil

Pre-Flighter's Log

Date: 13/11/08

Flight No: B 420

Pre-Flighter: MS

No.	✓ or x	Location	Action	Comments
1	☒	Hangar	Collect spanners for core chem	
<u>Aircraft Cabin: Power-up</u>				
2	☒	Core Chemistry	Gases x 3 ON	
3	☒	Cabin	All Racks Checked	
4	☒	Core Chemistry	Instruments Checked OK	KT
5	☒	Core Chemistry	CO Flows Checked OK	KT
6	☒	Aft CorCon	All reqd CBs made	
7	☒	Fore CorCon	CBs made, PCs ON	
8	☒	HORACE	Optical Disk loaded	
9	☒	HORACE	Recording data	
10	☒	HORACE	DLU Status Checked	
11	☒	HORACE	HORACE Status Checked	
12	☒	Satcom H	Power LED ON	
13	☒	Nevzorov	Checked and OFF	
14	☒	Cameras Pictures	Checked x 4 OK	
15	☒	Video Laptop	Checked onboard	
16	☒	FWVS	Set up & check on AUTO	T80 work
17	☒	Delced Rosemount	Heater Checked then OFF	
18	☒	Heimann	Calibration Checked	
19	☒	TWC	Fitted & signals checked	STAT = 4088
20	☒	GE	Balance checked then back to DP	
21	☒	GPS (XR5M)	Checked	
22	☒	Satcom C	Checked	
23	☒	Video x 2	Records okay, Rewind	

No.	✓ or x	Location	Action	Comments
24	☒	Miss. Sci Laptop	Checked Onboard	In cockpit
25	☒	CNC	Butanol filled	
26	☒	Dry Neph	Power up & Zero Cal	JB
27	☒	PSAP	Pre-flight log actions complete	JB
28	☒	CGPS	CBs and PC ON	
<u>External Checks</u>				
29	☒	Turb Probe	Clean if reqd, Photo taken	
30	☒	JW	Cleaned & Checked	
31	☒	DI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
32	☒	NDI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
33	☒	Nevzorov	Cleaned/windings checked	
34	☒	GE	Cleaned & Checked	
35	☒	Lower BBRs	Domes cleaned/checked	
36	☒	Camera Windows	Cleaned	
37	☒	Heimann	Lens checked OK	
38	☒	TWC Cover	Fitted if required	
39	☒	All other covers	Removed	
40	☐	Pre-flight Bag	Returned to hold	** Check no butanol**
41	☐	Tools	Check ALL in Toolkit	
42	☐	Tools	Avalon informed	
<u>Avalon Checks</u>				
44	☒	Upper BBRs Checked & Cleaned		Signed a) Nil b) 1-2 drops c) 1/4 full or more
45	☒	ICEX applied		
46	☒	Turb Probe - Traps emptied, detail contents -		
47	☒	Turb Probe - Traps dried and resealed		

CVI log

11/13/08 8:39:13 AM cpc and pcasp getting sensible readings
 11/13/08 8:39:55 AM turn on counterflow to dry the system down
 11/13/08 9:36:10 AM some counts on first lyman zero
 11/13/08 9:38:17 AM close lid for take off
 11/13/08 10:06:22 AM into aerosol mode
 11/13/08 10:12:29 AM into aerosol mode
 11/13/08 10:12:32 AM into aerosol mode
 11/13/08 10:12:36 AM into aerosol mode
 11/13/08 10:12:46 AM set floes and counterflow ready bfor th in cloud legs
 11/13/08 10:13:33 AM lyman to reference for cloud passage
 11/13/08 10:16:28 AM lyman to sample
 11/13/08 10:17:32 AM lyman to sample
 11/13/08 10:17:37 AM lyman to sample
 11/13/08 10:22:35 AM gone to cvi mode with ams
 11/13/08 10:23:37 AM gone to cvi mode with ams
 11/13/08 10:24:33 AM very far from zero below cloud - was this drizzle drops? it
 didn't seem as though there would be any
 11/13/08 10:26:10 AM very far from zero below cloud - was this drizzle drops? it
 didn't seem as though there would be any
 11/13/08 10:26:18 AM very far from zero below cloud - was this drizzle drops? it
 didn't seem as though there would be any
 11/13/08 10:26:20 AM very far from zero below cloud - was this drizzle drops? it
 didn't seem as though there would be any
 11/13/08 10:26:24 AM very far from zero below cloud - was this drizzle drops? it
 didn't seem as though there would be any
 11/13/08 10:26:28 AM very far from zero below cloud - was this drizzle drops? it
 didn't seem as though there would be any
 11/13/08 10:26:48 AM very far from zero below cloud - was this drizzle drops? it
 didn't seem as though there would be any
 11/13/08 10:26:53 AM very far from zero below cloud - was this drizzle drops? it
 didn't seem as though there would be any
 11/13/08 10:26:56 AM very far from zero below cloud - was this drizzle drops? it
 didn't seem as though there would be any
 11/13/08 10:26:59 AM very far from zero below cloud - was this drizzle drops? it
 didn't seem as though there would be any
 11/13/08 10:30:17 AM more structure on lwc from jw, nv than cvi, so drop dilution
 factor
 11/13/08 10:31:04 AM more structure on lwc from jw, nv than cvi, so drop dilution
 factor
 11/13/08 10:31:12 AM more structure on lwc from jw, nv than cvi, so drop dilution
 factor
 11/13/08 10:39:32 AM into counterflow mode
 11/13/08 10:39:57 AM smps sees a shift in mode of the dsize of residual particles when
 we hit the areas of increased lwc
 11/13/08 10:40:31 AM this could be due to shattering of the larger droplets, leading
 to smaller residuals than might be expected, look at ratio of 2dc, 2ds anfd
 fssp, cdp etc
 11/13/08 10:40:53 AM organics increases correlated with lwc, is this just some wash of
 effect?
 11/13/08 10:41:05 AM organics increases correlated with lwc, is this just some wash of
 effect?
 11/13/08 10:41:08 AM organics increases correlated with lwc, is this just some wash of
 effect?
 11/13/08 10:48:27 AM drizzle blip? on cpc but not on ccn rack
 11/13/08 10:48:52 AM
 11/13/08 10:55:50 AM into cvi mode
 11/13/08 10:56:13 AM ams on as well
 11/13/08 10:56:20 AM ams on as well
 11/13/08 11:02:16 AM ams on as well
 11/13/08 11:02:25 AM ams on as well
 11/13/08 11:04:00 AM wide spread in verticle wind on this leg
 11/13/08 11:04:45 AM wide spread in verticle wind on this leg
 11/13/08 11:04:49 AM wide spread in verticle wind on this leg
 11/13/08 11:07:05 AM ly to reference for zero aboce cloud
 11/13/08 11:08:40 AM zero lyman
 11/13/08 11:08:59 AM zero lyman
 11/13/08 11:09:08 AM zero lyman

11/13/08 11:09:50 AM back to lyman sample
11/13/08 11:11:57 AM into counterflow below cloud base
11/13/08 11:12:11 AM into counterflow below cloud base
11/13/08 11:12:19 AM into counterflow below cloud base
11/13/08 11:12:22 AM into counterflow below cloud base
11/13/08 11:12:28 AM drizzle on 2ds
11/13/08 11:21:18 AM drizzle on 2ds
11/13/08 11:21:22 AM drizzle on 2ds
11/13/08 11:21:25 AM drizzle on 2ds
11/13/08 11:21:27 AM drizzle on 2ds
11/13/08 11:21:29 AM drizzle on 2ds
11/13/08 11:22:25 AM heavy drizzle now - can see on cpc/pcasp
11/13/08 11:22:31 AM about 300 μ m
11/13/08 11:27:29 AM into cvi
11/13/08 11:28:11 AM back into cvi mode for sub cloud leg
11/13/08 11:32:59 AM lots of drizzle on 5.2 as well
11/13/08 11:33:59 AM into counterflow mode now, ams also
11/13/08 11:34:13 AM didnt change before hitting cloud base
11/13/08 11:34:30 AM didnt change before hitting cloud base
11/13/08 11:34:35 AM didnt change before hitting cloud base
11/13/08 11:39:06 AM high lwc on nv, jw een accounting for offsets, we are seeing structure but not the quantity
11/13/08 11:44:05 AM popped into cloud top
11/13/08 11:44:53 AM lwc does not drop to zero when we pop out of cloud - lag, smoothing, etc/
11/13/08 11:45:56 AM leave in counterflow until through cloud
11/13/08 11:46:14 AM leave in counterflow until through cloud
11/13/08 11:46:18 AM leave in counterflow until through cloud
11/13/08 11:46:24 AM leave in counterflow until through cloud
11/13/08 11:47:06 AM cpc trace mirrors jw etc, but lycwc seems less responsive
11/13/08 11:48:29 AM counterflow is off below cloud
11/13/08 11:48:56 AM lots of drizzle on cpc
11/13/08 11:52:43 AM 500ft aerosol leg
11/13/08 11:55:25 AM 500ft aerosol leg
11/13/08 11:58:09 AM some drizzle, very variable moisture structure
11/13/08 12:04:33 PM into cvi mode, cloud all over the place at low level as well
11/13/08 12:07:14 PM into cvi mode, cloud all over the place at low level as well
11/13/08 12:07:18 PM into cvi mode, cloud all over the place at low level as well
11/13/08 12:07:42 PM 2ds big drops
11/13/08 12:08:35 PM warm the tip, try to get the drops evAPORATED
11/13/08 12:16:32 PM EXTEND THE RUN FOR 3 MINUTES!
11/13/08 12:22:08 PM have we just flown though a POC?
11/13/08 12:22:37 PM drop ams flow for next cloud passage
11/13/08 12:25:10 PM keep in counterflow mode for this profile, to try and look at the drizzle below cloud
11/13/08 12:28:46 PM switch to aerosol mode, not much drizzle in this location
11/13/08 12:30:28 PM switch to aerosol mode, not much drizzle in this location
11/13/08 12:30:36 PM back under drizzle
11/13/08 12:32:31 PM 10-20 at 300 μ m from 2dc
11/13/08 12:32:57 PM split this run 5min aero 5min cvi
11/13/08 12:33:15 PM into cvi now
11/13/08 12:33:39 PM into cvi now
11/13/08 12:34:14 PM spike
11/13/08 12:34:56 PM spike
11/13/08 12:35:13 PM spike
11/13/08 12:35:17 PM spike
11/13/08 12:36:51 PM we see spike in cpc, but not very much liquid water when we have a drizzle incident
11/13/08 12:41:42 PM we see spike in cpc, but not very much liquid water when we have a drizzle incident
11/13/08 12:42:11 PM we see spike in cpc, but not very much liquid water when we have a drizzle incident
11/13/08 12:42:20 PM ams on to cvi, m fow input as 0.72
11/13/08 12:43:38 PM ams on to cvi, m fow input as 0.72
11/13/08 12:43:58 PM ams on to cvi, m fow input as 0.72
11/13/08 12:45:39 PM still very high on cpc indicating shattering of the drizzle particles
11/13/08 12:48:58 PM still very high on cpc indicating shattering of the drizzle particles

11/13/08 12:49:02 PM still very high on cpc indicating shattering of the drizzle particles
11/13/08 12:52:29 PM still very high on cpc indicating shattering of the drizzle particles
11/13/08 12:52:32 PM still very high on cpc indicating shattering of the drizzle particles
11/13/08 12:57:03 PM into aerosol for the far west profile climb, lyman to reference for the cloud passage
11/13/08 12:57:40 PM very lowcpc counts way out here, it is a clean day
11/13/08 12:58:37 PM very lowcpc counts way out here, it is a clean day
11/13/08 12:59:17 PM very lowcpc counts way out here, it is a clean day
11/13/08 12:59:23 PM drizzle
11/13/08 1:00:59 PM through cloud now
11/13/08 1:01:27 PM through cloud now
11/13/08 1:01:30 PM through cloud now
11/13/08 1:01:32 PM through cloud now
11/13/08 1:02:02 PM out of cloud
11/13/08 1:02:18 PM out of cloud
11/13/08 1:02:21 PM out of cloud
11/13/08 1:05:48 PM end of vocals
11/13/08 2:38:23 PM end of vocals
11/13/08 2:57:04 PM belts on at 10kft - into counterfow mode - set to 3.0
11/13/08 2:57:39 PM belts on at 10kft - into counterfow mode - set to 3.0

ARIES flight log

Flight: 13420

page 1 of 1

Date: 13/Nov/2008

Operator(s): S. Rogers

Res: 1

Gain A: 2 B: 2

Loc./Notes: VOCALS

Scans: either "[I/GMs]X[co-adds]", or "[stop DRS time]" if in start/stop, or "[macro name]". View: mirror angle.

DRS time	Flt ptrn	Scans	View	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Comments
083055	On the ground		CH	C	71	31	ColdHollin script
0959	Take off						
100436	6000ft		NZ	O	71	30	Nad Zen Long Run ^{30 sec}
101107	↓		-	C	71	31	6000ft → 5000ft
101703	5000ft		NZ	O	71	31	Nad Zen Long Run ^{30 sec} <small>Climb during last Nad</small>
104513	2400ft		NZ	O	71	31	Nad Zen Long Run 30 sec Ear 1055
1116	↑ 2000ft		NZ	O	71	30	Nad Zen Long Run 30 sec 8/8 SE in abax. ↑ Opp. Started early, so cal is in climb Ear 1127
115225	500ft		NZ	O	71	31	Nad Zen Long Run 30 sec.
1207	3000ft		CH	C	71	31	ColdHollin In cloud.
122827	500ft		NZ	O	71	31	Nad Zen Long Run 30 sec Ear 1240
	↑						Scans 1 during profile at ~ FL180
131651	FL230		N	C	71	31	Nadir Long Run 3 min
132148	"			C	71	31	Scans 2
132400	"		Z	O	71	30	Zenith Long Run 3 min Ci above?
132958	"		N	O	71	31	Nadir Long Run 3 min Scans 3
133313	"		Z	O	71	31	Zenith Long Run 3 min
134029	"		N	O	71	31	Nadir Long Run 3 min Scans 4
134332	"		Z	O	71	31	Zenith Long Run 3 min
135030	"		N	O	71	31	Nadir Long Run 3 min Scans 5
135419	"		Z	O	71	31	Zenith Long Run 3 min
140144	"		N	O	71	31	Nadir Long Run 3 min Scans 6
140524	"		Z	O	71	31	Zenith Long Run 3 min
141240	"		N	O	71	31	Nadir Long Run 3 min Scans 7
141623	"		Z	O	71	30	Zenith Long Run 3 min
141929	"		N	O	71	30	Nadir Long Run 3 min Scans 8 (during cal) (to extra scans)
142147	"		Z	O	71	31	Zenith Long Run 3 min
142332	"		N	O	71	31	Nadir Long Run 3 min Scans 9
142716	"		Z	O	71	31	Zenith Long Run 3 min
143413	"		N	O	71	31	Nadir Long Run 3 min Scans 10
143814	"		Z	O	71	31	Zenith Long Run 3 min Ear 1442

B420_SWS_SHIMS_EventLog

```

08:22:49.94 --- - - - -
08:22:49.95 --- - - - - +++ SOFTWARE START/RESTART +++
08:22:49.95 --- - - - - +++ hh:mm:ss.ff / Instr / Posn / Period /
tVIS/ tNIR / Comment +++
08:22:49.95 --- - - - - +++ Flight no. B420
08:22:49.95 --- - - - -
08:22:56.24 SWS - 100 - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
08:23:11.70 SWS - - 40 - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 40ms.
08:23:13.78 SWS - - - 40 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 40ms.
08:23:17.85 USH - 100 - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
08:23:22.65 USH - - 40 - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 40ms.
08:23:24.52 USH - - - 40 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 40ms.
08:23:28.10 LSH - 100 - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
08:23:32.56 LSH - - 100 - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 100ms.
08:23:43.99 SWS - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
08:23:44.08 USH - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
08:23:44.17 LSH - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
08:24:01.68 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
08:24:01.69 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
08:24:01.69 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
08:24:03.33 SWS - - - - Idling
08:24:03.44 USH - - - - Idling
08:24:03.86 LSH - - - - Idling
08:24:06.42 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
08:24:06.42 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
08:24:06.43 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
08:26:51.45 SWS - - - - ERROR: Failed to initialise telescope.
08:27:34.28 SWS - - - - Telescope disabled.
08:27:38.64 SWS - - - - Telescope motor initialised.
08:27:49.04 SWS -0.0 - - - - Telescope sent to -6.000
08:27:51.77 SWS -6.0 - - - - Telescope sent to 174.000
08:27:53.44 SWS 170.7 - - - - Telescope stopped.
08:28:02.07 SWS 174.0 - - - - Telescope sent to -6.000
08:28:03.74 SWS -2.4 - - - - Telescope stopped.
08:28:22.71 --- - - - - *** SWS head cleaned
08:28:43.75 --- - - - - *** Start up
08:28:54.44 --- - - - - *** All ok
08:28:58.43 SWS - - - - Idling
08:28:58.48 LSH - - - - Idling
08:28:58.50 USH - - - - Idling
08:29:01.02 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
08:29:01.02 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
08:29:01.03 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
08:29:01.86 SWS - - - - Idling
08:29:02.29 USH - - - - Idling
08:29:02.65 LSH - - - - Idling
08:29:04.48 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
08:29:04.48 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
08:29:04.48 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
08:29:21.55 --- - - - - *** Assuming all shutters working
08:29:45.05 --- - - - - *** Nil cloud above slight mist vis 8Km
08:30:23.40 --- - - - - *** LSH NIR giving no signal - so no
distraction
08:30:41.37 --- - - - - *** Good flat line on all others
09:39:54.92 SWS - - - - Idling
09:39:54.94 LSH - - - - Idling
09:39:54.97 USH - - - - Idling
09:39:56.36 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:39:56.37 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:39:56.38 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:39:57.22 SWS - - - - Idling
09:39:57.63 USH - - - - Idling
09:39:57.83 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:39:57.83 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:39:58.02 LSH - - - - Idling
09:40:51.51 --- - - - - *** Still nil cloud. Vis >10K
09:41:04.88 --- - - - - *** T/O will be start of profile 1

```

09:41:22.98	---	-	-	-	*** SWS head to rear for T/O
09:41:35.54	SWS	-6.0	-	-	Telescope sent to 80.713
09:41:36.67	SWS	80.7	-	-	Telescope stopped.
09:42:02.04	---	-	-	-	*** Cool box temp 11C
09:44:19.21	---	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
09:44:22.42	---	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
09:44:25.65	USH	-	-	-	Idling
09:44:25.66	SWS	-	-	-	Idling
09:44:30.12	USH	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:44:30.14	SWS	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:44:30.16	LSH	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:44:30.96	USH	-	-	-	Idling
09:44:31.19	SWS	-	-	-	Idling
09:44:31.97	LSH	-	-	-	Idling
09:44:34.96	SWS	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:44:34.96	LSH	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:44:34.97	USH	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:00:41.57	LSH	-	-	100	NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 100ms.
10:00:45.72	SWS	80.7	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
10:00:46.86	SWS	174.0	-	-	Telescope stopped.
10:01:55.05	---	-	-	-	*** Start of profile 1
10:02:48.51	---	-	-	-	***
10:03:45.17	---	-	-	-	*** start of p1 095907 below nil cloud vis
>10K					
10:04:37.27	---	-	-	-	*** Start of run at FL060 100426
10:05:18.97	SWS	-	-	-	Idling
10:05:19.01	LSH	-	-	-	Idling
10:05:19.03	USH	-	-	-	Idling
10:05:21.31	SWS	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:05:21.31	LSH	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:05:21.32	USH	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:05:22.14	SWS	-	-	-	Idling
10:05:22.54	USH	-	-	-	Idling
10:05:22.96	LSH	-	-	-	Idling
10:05:27.91	SWS	174.0	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
10:05:29.62	SWS	-5.0	-	-	Telescope stopped.
10:05:30.98	SWS	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:05:30.98	LSH	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:05:31.00	USH	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:07:12.23	---	-	-	-	*** Approaching 8/8 Sc5 moving head to N
10:07:15.16	SWS	-6.0	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
10:07:16.84	SWS	171.6	-	-	Telescope stopped.
10:07:21.31	SWS	-	-	-	Idling
10:07:21.34	LSH	-	-	-	Idling
10:07:21.38	USH	-	-	-	Idling
10:07:23.96	SWS	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:07:23.97	LSH	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:07:23.97	USH	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:07:24.81	SWS	-	-	-	Idling
10:07:25.22	USH	-	-	-	Idling
10:07:25.63	LSH	-	-	-	Idling
10:07:27.11	LSH	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:07:27.12	USH	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:07:27.13	SWS	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:08:39.08	---	-	-	-	*** Coolbox at 13C
10:09:00.94	---	-	-	-	*** over 8/8 Sc5 below nil
10:11:39.79	---	-	-	-	*** Start of P2 descent to FL005
10:11:55.65	---	-	-	-	*** 101107
10:13:39.23	---	-	-	-	*** into 8/8 Sc5
10:14:27.78	---	-	-	-	*** at FL037
10:14:39.89	---	-	-	-	*** Below 8/8 Sc5
10:14:51.67	---	-	-	-	*** at FL026
10:16:28.08	---	-	-	-	*** S5 now 7/8 coolbox 12C
10:17:17.23	---	-	-	-	*** Start of run at FL005 101702
10:17:20.94	SWS	174.0	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
10:17:22.62	SWS	-4.6	-	-	Telescope stopped.
10:20:15.74	LSH	-	-	-	Idling
10:20:15.75	SWS	-	-	-	Idling
10:20:15.76	USH	-	-	-	Idling

```

10:20:17.40 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
10:20:17.42 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
10:20:17.42 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
10:20:18.26 SWS - - - - Idling
10:20:18.69 USH - - - - Idling
10:20:19.08 LSH - - - - Idling
10:20:22.53 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
10:20:22.53 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
10:20:22.54 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
10:20:26.46 SWS -6.0 - - - - Telescope sent to 174.000
10:20:28.16 SWS 172.8 - - - - Telescope stopped.
10:21:25.00 SWS 174.0 - - - - Telescope sent to -6.000
10:21:26.73 SWS -5.0 - - - - Telescope stopped.
10:22:19.41 --- - - - - *** Start of p3 below 6/8 Sc5
10:22:55.08 --- - - - - *** 102204
10:24:51.14 --- - - - - *** Into cloud
10:25:10.37 --- - - - - ***
10:25:10.43 LSH - - - - Idling
10:25:10.45 USH - - - - Idling
10:25:10.53 SWS - - - - Idling
10:25:10.58 SWS - - - - Idling
10:25:13.92 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
10:25:13.93 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
10:25:13.94 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
10:25:14.97 USH - - - - Idling
10:25:15.21 SWS - - - - Idling
10:25:15.39 LSH - - - - Idling
10:25:18.28 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
10:25:18.28 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
10:25:18.30 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
10:25:25.54 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
10:25:30.51 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
10:25:36.61 USH - - - - Idling
10:25:36.62 SWS - - - - Idling
10:25:36.69 LSH - - - - Idling
10:25:39.68 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
10:25:39.69 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
10:25:39.70 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
10:25:40.56 SWS - - - - Idling
10:25:40.94 USH - - - - Idling
10:25:41.35 LSH - - - - Idling
10:25:43.94 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
10:25:43.95 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
10:25:43.96 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
10:26:07.40 --- - - - - *** Start of run 3 FL034 102537
10:26:17.04 --- - - - - *** In thin 7/8 Sc5
10:26:39.84 --- - - - - *** Coolbox at 10C
10:28:19.52 LSH - - 40 - - VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 40ms.
10:28:19.53 LSH - - - 40 - - NIR int.time changed from 100ms to 40ms.
10:28:26.91 LSH - - 600 - - VIS int.time changed from 40ms to 600ms.
10:28:26.92 LSH - - - 600 - - NIR int.time changed from 40ms to 600ms.
10:28:32.98 LSH - - 100 - - VIS int.time changed from 600ms to 100ms.
10:28:32.99 LSH - - - 100 - - NIR int.time changed from 600ms to 100ms.
10:28:57.20 --- - - - - *** Not
10:29:11.42 --- - - - - ***
10:30:34.21 --- - - - - *** Wow! What happened?! LSH requesting init
10:31:06.61 --- - - - - *** SWS dropped out and motor driver went to
settings mode
10:31:30.17 --- - - - - *** Not sure what button I pressed but suspect
I'm losing the software
10:32:47.67 --- - - - - *** Will restart software
10:33:09.54 --- - - - - Reset shutters.

10:36:27.31 --- - - - -
10:36:27.31 --- - - - - +++ SOFTWARE START/RESTART +++
10:36:27.31 --- - - - - +++ hh:mm:ss.ff / Instr / Posn / Period /
tVIS/ tNIR / Comment +++
10:36:27.31 --- - - - - +++ Flight no. B420b

```

10:36:27.31	---	-	-	-	-	
10:37:02.11	SWS	-	-	-	-	Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
10:37:03.47	USH	-	-	-	-	Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
10:37:04.01	LSH	-	-	-	-	Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
10:37:14.87	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:37:14.87	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:37:14.88	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:37:15.34	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
10:37:15.64	USH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
10:37:15.83	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:37:15.88	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:37:15.96	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:37:17.85	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:37:17.85	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:37:17.85	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:37:25.55	SWS	-	100	-	-	Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
10:37:29.17	SWS	-	-	40	-	VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 40ms.
10:37:30.72	SWS	-	-	-	40	NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 40ms.
10:37:34.70	USH	-	100	-	-	Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
10:37:38.69	USH	-	-	40	-	VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 40ms.
10:37:41.05	USH	-	-	-	40	NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 40ms.
10:37:44.59	LSH	-	100	-	-	Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
10:37:48.38	LSH	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 100ms.
10:37:50.09	LSH	-	-	-	100	NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 100ms.
10:38:52.98	SWS	-	-	-	-	Telescope motor initialised.
10:38:56.97	SWS	-	-	-	-	Telescope disabled.
10:39:10.36	SWS	-	-	-	-	Telescope motor initialised.
10:39:18.02	SWS	0.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
10:40:26.19	---	-	-	-	-	*** Ok restart after drop out
10:40:59.04	---	-	-	-	-	*** Below 8/8 Sc5 in profile descent
10:41:15.98	---	-	-	-	-	*** Not convinced LSH has worked at all today
10:42:11.11	---	-	-	-	-	*** This is P5
10:42:26.29	---	-	-	-	-	*** to 50ft
10:42:39.38	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
10:42:41.05	SWS	170.9	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
10:43:01.60	---	-	-	-	-	*** Start of P6 to FL024
10:43:46.17	---	-	-	-	-	*** P6 was at 104237 below 7/8 Sc5
10:45:29.29	---	-	-	-	-	*** Start of run at FL024 below 7/8 Sc5 104513
10:45:33.97	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:45:33.98	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:45:34.06	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:45:37.29	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
10:45:38.92	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
10:45:38.99	SWS	-4.6	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
10:45:44.25	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:45:44.26	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:45:44.28	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:45:45.53	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:45:45.82	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:45:46.26	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:45:51.96	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:45:51.96	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:45:51.97	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:45:52.99	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:45:53.21	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:45:53.31	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:45:53.31	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:45:53.40	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:45:53.42	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:45:54.15	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:45:54.43	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:45:55.17	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:46:01.66	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
10:46:07.06	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:46:07.06	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:46:07.07	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:46:53.65	---	-	-	-	-	*** Ok appear to have lost Vis on SWS. Will
restart module						
10:47:03.39	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.

10:47:04.23	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:47:58.66	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:47:59.49	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:48:01.03	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:48:01.87	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:48:06.17	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:48:06.24	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:48:06.26	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:48:06.43	USH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
10:48:07.06	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:48:07.46	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:48:07.86	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:48:10.02	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:48:10.04	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:48:10.06	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:48:10.49	USH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
10:48:10.86	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:48:11.09	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:48:11.89	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:48:12.15	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:48:12.17	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:48:12.22	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:48:13.00	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:48:13.21	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:48:14.01	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:48:18.37	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
10:48:22.18	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
10:48:27.22	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:48:27.24	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:48:27.26	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:48:27.70	USH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
10:48:28.10	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:48:28.31	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:48:29.11	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:48:58.54	---	-	-	-	-	*** Now upper SHIMS is not working
10:49:01.89	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:49:02.16	USH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
10:49:02.74	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:49:25.19	---	-	-	-	-	*** Going to restart all modules
10:49:52.85	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:49:52.90	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:49:52.95	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:49:59.46	SWS	-	-	-	-	Instrument closed.
10:50:01.37	USH	-	-	-	-	Instrument closed.
10:50:03.28	LSH	-	-	-	-	Instrument closed.
10:51:28.36	SWS	-	-	-	-	Initialization: VIS FAILED NIR OK
10:51:28.46	USH	-	-	-	-	Initialization: VIS FAILED NIR OK
10:51:28.55	LSH	-	-	-	-	Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
10:51:38.33	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:51:38.33	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:51:38.34	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:51:39.75	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:51:39.84	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:51:40.29	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:51:42.32	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:51:42.33	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:51:42.33	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:52:01.69	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
10:52:07.94	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:52:08.00	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:52:08.03	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:52:13.44	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:52:13.44	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:52:13.45	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:52:14.28	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:52:14.69	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:52:15.09	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:52:18.72	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:52:18.72	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.

```

10:52:18.73 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
10:52:26.88 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
10:52:32.29 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
10:52:37.99 SWS - - - - Idling
10:52:38.02 USH - - - - Idling
10:52:38.09 LSH - - - - Idling
10:52:44.33 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
10:52:44.34 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
10:52:44.34 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
10:52:45.17 SWS - - - - Idling
10:52:45.58 USH - - - - Idling
10:52:45.98 LSH - - - - Idling
10:52:47.64 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
10:52:47.64 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
10:52:47.65 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
10:53:02.70 --- - - - - *** Coolbox at 12c
10:53:10.84 SWS - - - - Idling
10:53:10.85 LSH - - - - Idling
10:53:10.92 USH - - - - Idling
10:53:16.99 SWS - - - - Instrument closed.
10:53:19.21 USH - - - - Instrument closed.
10:53:20.96 LSH - - - - Instrument closed.
10:53:30.60 SWS - - - - Telescope disabled.
10:53:33.54 --- - - - - *** SHUTTING DOWN...
10:53:33.76 SWS - - - - Telescope motor control quit.

10:57:42.60 --- - - - -
10:57:42.61 --- - - - - +++ SOFTWARE START/RESTART +++
10:57:42.61 --- - - - - +++ hh:mm:ss.ff / Instr / Posn / Period /
tVIS/ tNIR / Comment +++
10:57:42.61 --- - - - - +++ Flight no. B420c
10:57:42.61 --- - - - -
10:57:59.85 SWS - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
10:58:01.24 USH - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
10:58:01.61 LSH - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
10:58:09.21 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
10:58:13.39 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
10:58:21.31 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
10:58:21.31 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
10:58:21.32 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
10:58:22.30 USH - - - - Idling
10:58:22.39 LSH - - - - Idling
10:58:22.49 SWS - - - - Idling
10:58:25.54 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
10:58:25.54 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
10:58:25.54 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
10:59:06.90 --- - - - - *** Re-start after loosing Vis from SWS and
USH
10:59:34.79 --- - - - - *** VIS is back but with no NIR
11:00:07.09 USH - - - - Idling
11:00:07.16 SWS - - - - Idling
11:00:07.18 LSH - - - - Idling
11:00:09.57 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
11:00:44.10 SWS - - - - Instrument closed.
11:00:45.72 USH - - - - Instrument closed.
11:00:47.90 LSH - - - - Instrument closed.
11:01:21.51 --- - - - - *** All modules closed and power removed
11:06:45.30 SWS - - - - Initialization: VIS FAILED NIR OK
11:06:45.39 USH - - - - Initialization: VIS FAILED NIR OK
11:06:45.48 LSH - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
11:06:55.30 SWS - 100 - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
11:07:01.54 SWS - - 40 - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 40ms.
11:07:03.53 SWS - - - 40 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 40ms.
11:07:07.37 USH - 100 - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
11:07:13.16 USH - - 40 - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 40ms.
11:07:15.31 USH - - - 40 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 40ms.
11:07:19.68 LSH - 100 - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
11:07:25.03 LSH - - 40 - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 40ms.

```

11:07:27.13	LSH	-	-	-	40	NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 40ms.
11:07:30.35	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
11:07:33.65	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
11:07:57.48	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:07:57.48	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:07:57.48	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:07:58.84	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:07:58.95	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:07:59.06	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:08:17.46	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
11:08:20.65	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
11:08:30.67	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:08:30.68	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:08:30.72	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:08:31.51	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:08:31.73	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:08:31.95	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:09:39.99	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:09:39.99	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:09:40.01	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:09:40.82	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:09:41.06	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:09:41.27	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:09:52.07	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:09:52.07	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:09:52.09	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:10:23.44	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:10:23.51	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:10:23.52	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:10:32.00	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:10:32.00	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:10:32.01	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:10:32.84	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:10:33.06	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:10:33.28	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:10:36.94	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:10:36.95	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:10:36.95	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:10:58.54	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:10:58.56	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:10:58.57	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:11:06.17	SWS	-	-	-	-	Instrument closed.
11:11:07.94	USH	-	-	-	-	Instrument closed.
11:11:09.82	LSH	-	-	-	-	Instrument closed.
11:11:21.20	SWS	-	-	-	-	Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
11:11:21.30	USH	-	-	-	-	Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
11:11:21.39	LSH	-	-	-	-	Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
11:11:46.92	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:11:46.92	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:11:46.95	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:11:48.65	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:11:48.75	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:11:48.78	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:11:51.23	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:11:51.24	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:11:51.26	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:12:47.01	LSH	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 40ms to 100ms.
11:12:47.02	LSH	-	-	-	100	NIR int.time changed from 40ms to 100ms.
11:12:59.92	SWS	-	-	-	-	Telescope motor initialised.
11:13:08.14	SWS	0.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
11:13:50.01	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:13:50.02	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:13:50.11	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:13:59.48	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:13:59.48	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:13:59.49	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:14:00.32	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:14:00.72	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:14:01.12	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling

11:14:04.28	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:14:04.28	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:14:04.28	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:14:27.75	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
11:14:33.84	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:14:33.90	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:14:33.91	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:14:37.32	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:14:37.32	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:14:37.33	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:14:38.17	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:14:38.59	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:14:38.99	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:14:41.11	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:14:41.13	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:14:41.13	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:15:33.75	---	-	-	-	-	*** SWS and USH back in business I think
11:16:09.80	---	-	-	-	-	*** Start of profile climb
11:16:41.57	---	-	-	-	-	*** P10 111515
11:17:43.95	---	-	-	-	-	*** Start of run 5.1 at FL020 111725
11:18:53.69	---	-	-	-	-	*** 8/8 Sc5 with precip
11:20:12.29	---	-	-	-	-	*** Suggestion of 1/8 St7 fractus ahead though
suspectthats	what	we're	below	now		
11:20:55.05	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
11:20:56.73	SWS	170.9	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
11:21:21.52	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:21:21.52	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:21:21.54	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:21:22.94	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:21:22.94	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:21:22.95	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:21:23.79	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:21:24.19	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:21:24.59	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:21:28.69	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
11:21:30.36	SWS	-3.3	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
11:21:31.10	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:21:31.10	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:21:31.12	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:21:45.56	---	-	-	-	-	*** Sorry head to Nadir in error
11:28:34.61	---	-	-	-	-	*** Start of run 5.2 at FL025
11:28:55.20	---	-	-	-	-	*** May well enter St7 Fractus (or Cu1)
11:31:30.66	---	-	-	-	-	*** Main cloud layer remains 8/8 Sc5
11:31:48.51	---	-	-	-	-	*** and is still above
11:33:16.62	---	-	-	-	-	*** End of run and start of profile climb
11:33:22.29	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:33:22.29	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:33:22.30	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:33:24.35	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:33:24.35	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:33:24.36	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:33:25.40	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:33:25.64	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:33:25.82	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:33:29.19	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:33:29.19	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:33:29.20	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:34:38.71	---	-	-	-	-	*** in main Sc5 layer now
11:34:54.67	---	-	-	-	-	*** Start of run5.3
11:39:11.62	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
11:39:13.33	SWS	173.5	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
11:41:28.96	---	-	-	-	-	*** Coolbox at 10C
11:42:14.96	---	-	-	-	-	*** Sc5 now 7/8
11:42:18.88	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
11:42:20.59	SWS	-3.1	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
11:43:47.41	---	-	-	-	-	*** Sc5 now 5/8
11:43:56.11	---	-	-	-	-	*** Above cloud
11:45:09.89	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of run and start of profile 13 climb
114436						

11:45:15.88	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:45:15.95	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:45:15.98	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:45:18.92	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:45:18.92	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:45:18.92	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:45:19.78	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:45:20.20	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:45:20.60	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:45:24.10	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
11:45:27.29	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
11:45:30.51	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:45:30.51	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:45:30.51	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:45:57.92	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
11:45:58.77	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
11:45:59.58	SWS	172.2	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
11:46:11.44	---	-	-	-	-	*** Start of profile descent to 50ft
11:46:22.87	---	-	-	-	-	*** P14 114602
11:46:56.18	---	-	-	-	-	*** into cloud at FL040
11:48:14.99	---	-	-	-	-	*** Below cloud at FL028
11:48:52.16	---	-	-	-	-	*** 1/8 St7/Cu1 below 8/8 Sc5
11:50:22.48	---	-	-	-	-	*** In precip
11:52:03.59	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
11:52:05.26	SWS	-2.6	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
11:52:06.57	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:52:06.59	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:52:06.60	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:52:11.45	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:52:11.46	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:52:11.46	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:52:12.30	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:52:12.72	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:52:13.11	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:52:16.98	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:52:16.98	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:52:16.99	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:52:53.00	---	-	-	-	-	*** Start of run 6.1 at FL005 115225
11:53:30.35	---	-	-	-	-	*** Still below 1/8 St7/Cu1 which is below 7/8 Sc5
11:56:55.02	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
11:56:56.71	SWS	172.9	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
11:58:02.69	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
11:58:03.70	SWS	78.8	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
11:58:04.83	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
12:01:27.04	---	-	-	-	-	*** 2/8 Cu1 below 7/8 Sc5
12:02:42.29	---	-	-	-	-	*** Coolbox at 13C
12:04:03.53	---	-	-	-	-	*** Start of profile climb to FL035
12:04:07.16	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:04:07.21	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:04:07.23	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:04:09.71	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:04:09.72	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:04:09.72	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:04:10.80	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:04:11.03	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:04:11.19	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:04:14.98	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:04:14.98	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:04:14.98	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:04:53.44	---	-	-	-	-	*** P16 at 120351
12:05:25.67	---	-	-	-	-	*** 1/8 St7 2/8 Cu1 7/8 Sc5
12:06:04.22	---	-	-	-	-	*** Into main Sc5 layer at FL025
12:06:50.68	---	-	-	-	-	*** Start of run 6.2 at FL035 in cloud
12:07:17.15	---	-	-	-	-	*** 6.2 120649
12:09:12.90	---	-	-	-	-	*** Sc5 layer now6/8 drop to FL030 to remain in cloud
12:10:06.69	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
12:10:07.27	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.

12:10:08.39	SWS	173.3	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
12:13:11.80	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
12:13:13.49	SWS	-4.1	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
12:16:07.34	---	-	-	-	-	*** Cloud become very thin
12:16:38.95	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
12:16:39.55	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
12:16:40.61	SWS	171.8	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
12:17:59.88	---	-	-	-	-	*** Getting glimpses of sea sea below and sky
above whilst	in cloud					
12:20:09.01	---	-	-	-	-	*** start of profile 17 climb 121951
12:20:11.26	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:20:11.27	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:20:11.29	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:20:13.36	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:20:13.37	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:20:13.37	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:20:13.63	USH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
12:20:14.22	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:20:14.63	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:20:15.03	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:20:19.98	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:20:19.98	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:20:19.99	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:20:20.83	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:20:21.24	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:20:21.64	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:20:24.14	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:20:24.15	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:20:24.16	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:20:28.15	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
12:20:29.85	SWS	-4.6	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
12:21:05.10	---	-	-	-	-	*** Above cloud at FL039
12:21:22.62	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:21:22.64	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:21:22.68	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:21:25.48	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:21:25.48	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:21:25.50	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:21:26.32	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:21:26.77	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:21:27.13	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:21:29.17	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
12:21:34.09	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:21:34.10	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:21:34.10	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:22:02.18	---	-	-	-	-	*** 6/8 Sc5
12:22:08.62	---	-	-	-	-	*** Start
12:22:09.03	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
12:22:09.87	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
12:22:10.75	SWS	173.3	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
12:22:29.90	---	-	-	-	-	*** Start of profile 18 descent to 50ft 122208
12:23:27.21	---	-	-	-	-	*** Into cloud FL038
12:23:38.44	---	-	-	-	-	*** Coolbox at 10C
12:24:56.41	---	-	-	-	-	*** Below cloud FL022
12:27:00.32	---	-	-	-	-	*** 2/8 St7/Cu1 6/8 Sc5
12:27:56.34	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
12:27:58.06	SWS	-4.6	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
12:28:16.88	---	-	-	-	-	*** Start of P19
12:28:31.69	---	-	-	-	-	*** Start of run 7.1
12:28:34.09	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:28:34.12	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:28:34.15	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:28:35.18	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:28:35.18	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:28:35.21	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:28:36.02	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:28:36.46	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:28:36.90	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:28:39.68	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.

12:28:39.69	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:28:39.70	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:29:20.26	---	-	-	-	-	*** Start of run was at 122825
12:32:58.55	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
12:33:00.24	SWS	171.9	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
12:37:02.49	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
12:37:04.22	SWS	-5.7	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
12:37:29.09	---	-	-	-	-	*** No change in cloud type or amount
12:38:11.66	---	-	-	-	-	*** In precip
12:40:44.04	---	-	-	-	-	*** Start of profile 20 124010
12:40:54.99	---	-	-	-	-	*** In rain
12:42:03.05	---	-	-	-	-	*** in cloud
12:42:11.32	---	-	-	-	-	*** FL024
12:43:20.68	---	-	-	-	-	*** Start of 'in cloud' run 7.2 124304
12:43:22.72	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:43:22.73	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:43:22.79	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:43:25.21	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:43:25.22	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:43:25.23	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:43:26.05	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:43:26.47	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:43:26.87	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:43:29.40	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:43:29.40	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:43:29.41	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:44:04.08	---	-	-	-	-	*** In 7/8 Sc5 but near tops and thin
12:44:14.65	---	-	-	-	-	*** Coolbox 12C
12:46:07.72	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
12:46:09.43	SWS	172.4	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
12:48:50.28	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
12:48:51.99	SWS	-4.1	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
12:51:09.75	---	-	-	-	-	*** Again getting glimpses of sea and sky
12:52:21.14	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
12:52:22.86	SWS	173.3	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
12:53:33.46	---	-	-	-	-	*** Start of profile descent 21 to 50 ft125307
12:53:36.48	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:53:36.54	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:53:36.56	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:53:38.87	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:53:38.88	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:53:38.89	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:53:39.75	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:53:40.17	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:53:40.56	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:53:42.02	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:53:42.02	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:53:42.03	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:54:04.95	---	-	-	-	-	*** Turning 180 degrees
12:54:43.89	---	-	-	-	-	*** below cloud at fl020
12:57:26.10	---	-	-	-	-	*** 1/8 st7 fractus 3/8 cu1 6/8 sc5
12:57:58.00	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
12:57:59.68	SWS	-5.1	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
12:58:26.66	---	-	-	-	-	*** Start of profile 22 ascent to fl023 125756
13:00:48.82	---	-	-	-	-	*** in cloud at fl026
13:01:58.62	---	-	-	-	-	*** above 7/8 Sc5 at FL038
13:04:07.78	---	-	-	-	-	*** nil cloud above
13:12:42.43	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:12:42.46	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:12:42.50	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:12:44.27	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:12:44.27	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:12:44.29	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:12:44.54	USH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
13:12:45.22	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:12:45.34	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:12:46.19	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:12:47.61	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:12:47.62	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.

13:12:47.63	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:12:48.47	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:12:48.88	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:12:49.29	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:12:50.24	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:12:50.25	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:12:50.26	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:12:53.50	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
13:12:55.20	SWS	172.8	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
13:13:15.45	---	-	-	-	-	*** Sonde 1
13:14:05.24	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
13:14:06.92	SWS	-3.3	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
13:16:51.80	---	-	-	-	-	*** coolbox at 12C
13:17:09.46	---	-	-	-	-	*** Start of run 8 131651
13:17:32.05	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
13:17:33.78	SWS	173.2	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
13:19:24.18	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
13:19:25.90	SWS	-5.7	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
13:19:39.69	---	-	-	-	-	*** Bit keen to anticipate next sonde
13:21:05.38	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
13:21:07.05	SWS	170.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
13:22:55.92	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
13:22:57.64	SWS	-4.9	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
13:23:14.60	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:23:14.66	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:23:14.80	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:23:17.05	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:23:17.06	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:23:17.09	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:23:17.59	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
13:23:17.94	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:23:18.35	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:23:18.76	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:23:23.32	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:23:23.33	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:23:23.34	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:29:51.45	---	-	-	-	-	*** Cloud still 7/8 Sc5 below with nil above
13:31:26.76	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
13:31:28.50	SWS	173.9	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
13:33:02.66	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
13:33:04.43	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
13:33:16.81	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:33:16.87	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:33:16.90	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:33:18.97	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:33:18.98	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:33:18.99	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:33:19.82	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:33:20.26	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:33:20.64	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:33:22.09	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:33:22.10	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:33:22.11	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:42:01.34	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
13:42:03.06	SWS	172.8	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
13:43:18.19	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
13:43:19.91	SWS	-5.3	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
13:43:28.69	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:43:28.71	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:43:28.78	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:43:30.55	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:43:30.55	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:43:30.56	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:43:30.82	USH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
13:43:31.42	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:43:31.65	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:43:32.44	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:43:38.42	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:43:38.42	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.

13:43:38.44	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:43:39.28	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:43:39.69	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:43:40.12	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:43:42.33	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:43:42.33	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:43:42.34	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:52:16.57	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
13:52:18.37	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
13:54:09.87	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
13:54:11.56	SWS	-3.2	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
13:54:23.83	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:54:23.89	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:54:23.92	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:54:25.57	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:54:25.57	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:54:25.58	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:54:26.43	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:54:26.84	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:54:27.26	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:54:29.41	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:54:29.41	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:54:29.43	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:01:42.34	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
14:01:44.40	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
14:01:46.12	SWS	173.5	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
14:01:57.55	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
14:01:59.27	SWS	-5.4	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
14:02:29.46	---	-	-	-	-	*** oops - bit early again
14:03:47.49	---	-	-	-	-	*** cloud still
14:03:47.92	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
14:03:49.63	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
14:03:51.37	SWS	173.9	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
14:04:11.26	---	-	-	-	-	*** cloud still 7/8 Sc5 below nil above
14:05:16.60	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
14:05:18.36	SWS	-5.9	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
14:05:20.66	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:05:20.69	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:05:20.69	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:05:23.38	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:05:23.39	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:05:23.40	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:05:23.66	USH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
14:05:24.30	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:05:24.53	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:05:25.30	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:05:27.55	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:05:28.49	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:05:29.96	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:05:29.98	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:05:29.98	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:07:07.04	---	-	-	-	-	*** LSH making a late attempt to be join in
and be helpful						
14:07:21.16	---	-	-	-	-	*** but I'm not convinced by it's efforts
14:14:31.89	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
14:14:33.63	SWS	173.5	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
14:16:16.39	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
14:16:18.07	SWS	-3.9	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
14:16:20.42	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:16:20.48	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:16:20.50	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:16:23.01	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:16:23.04	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:16:23.05	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:16:23.30	USH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
14:16:23.94	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:16:24.32	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:16:24.72	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:16:36.60	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.

14:16:36.61	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:16:36.62	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:16:37.47	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:16:37.90	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:16:38.28	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:16:42.30	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:16:42.32	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:16:42.32	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:19:52.09	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
14:19:54.18	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
14:19:55.91	SWS	173.7	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
14:25:03.37	---	-	-	-	-	*** Dropped the ball on this sorry. Will
return to Zen after next sonde						
14:25:30.26	---	-	-	-	-	*** Cloud currently 8/8 Sc5 below nil above
14:27:08.58	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
14:27:10.34	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
14:27:13.33	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:27:13.37	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:27:13.38	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:27:29.40	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:27:30.37	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:27:36.49	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:27:36.49	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:27:36.51	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:27:36.76	USH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
14:27:37.38	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:27:37.54	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:27:38.34	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:27:42.29	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:27:43.21	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:27:46.36	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:27:46.37	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:27:46.39	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:34:54.66	---	-	-	-	-	*** Sc5 at 7/8 below
14:36:01.86	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
14:36:03.62	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
14:37:56.02	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
14:37:57.77	SWS	-5.9	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
14:38:01.89	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:38:01.95	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:38:01.96	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:38:05.46	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:38:05.46	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:38:05.48	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:38:05.74	USH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
14:38:06.36	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:38:06.78	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:38:07.18	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:38:10.59	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:38:11.48	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:38:14.42	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:38:14.43	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:38:14.44	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:40:42.16	---	-	-	-	-	*** USH giving bright dark measurements each
time now						
14:43:15.15	---	-	-	-	-	*** Start of profile 23 descent from FL023 to
0 at 144239						
14:43:22.43	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
14:43:24.14	SWS	173.2	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
14:45:42.53	---	-	-	-	-	*** Coolbox at 12C
14:47:20.66	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:47:20.70	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:47:20.77	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:47:28.28	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:47:28.55	USH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
14:47:29.16	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:47:32.06	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:47:32.40	USH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
14:47:33.01	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling

14:47:36.20	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:47:36.54	USH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
14:47:37.15	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:47:40.94	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:47:40.95	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:47:40.99	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:47:42.05	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:47:42.27	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:47:42.51	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:47:46.22	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:47:46.22	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:47:46.26	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:51:06.56	---	-	-	-	-	*** 7/8 Sc5 below looking increasingly thin
14:59:21.17	---	-	-	-	-	*** Sc5 5/8 below and looks like we're about
to clear the sheet						
14:59:54.12	---	-	-	-	-	*** Sc5 now 3/8
15:02:07.18	---	-	-	-	-	*** Sc5 1/8 below and decreasing
15:03:17.14	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of profile descent
15:15:47.11	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:15:47.12	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:15:47.18	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:15:52.16	SWS	-	-	-	-	Instrument closed.
15:15:53.78	USH	-	-	-	-	Instrument closed.
15:15:55.77	LSH	-	-	-	-	Instrument closed.
15:16:09.28	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 103.300
15:16:10.45	SWS	103.3	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
15:16:18.77	SWS	-	-	-	-	Telescope disabled.
15:16:39.70	---	-	-	-	-	*** SHUTTING DOWN...
15:16:39.88	SWS	-	-	-	-	Telescope motor control quit.

MISSING LOG SHEETS:

The following log sheets are not available for flight B420:

Log	Reason
Pre-flight log	No log available
Instrument Status	may not be correct – Flight Manager asked to check
De-brief	No debrief has been completed by the Mission Scientist
Cloud Physics Processing	No cloud physics processing logs are expected for VOCALS flights
Core Chemistry / TDLAS	no In Flight log except in cases of instrument problems
CCN log	CCN operator does not create a log sheet
Dry Neph	Operator does not create a log sheet
2D-S / CAPS	2D-S / CAPS operator does not create a log sheet
AMS log	AMS operator does not create a log sheet
PAN log	PAN operator does not create a log sheet
VACC	Operator does not create a log sheet

Document control

Revision	Date	Author	Comments
r0	16 Sep 2009	Doug Anderson	Initial version missing the above noted logs
r1			
r2			

Digital video recordings in avi format:

faam-video-dfc_faam_20081113_r0_b420_095338_1hz.avi
 faam-video-dfc_faam_20081113_r0_b420_105338_1hz.avi
 faam-video-dfc_faam_20081113_r0_b420_115338_1hz.avi
 faam-video-dfc_faam_20081113_r0_b420_125338_1hz.avi
 faam-video-dfc_faam_20081113_r0_b420_135338_1hz.avi
 faam-video-dfc_faam_20081113_r0_b420_145338_1hz.avi

faam-video-rfc_faam_20081113_r0_b420_095330_1hz.avi
 faam-video-rfc_faam_20081113_r0_b420_105330_1hz.avi
 faam-video-rfc_faam_20081113_r0_b420_115330_1hz.avi
 faam-video-rfc_faam_20081113_r0_b420_125330_1hz.avi
 faam-video-rfc_faam_20081113_r0_b420_135330_1hz.avi
 faam-video-rfc_faam_20081113_r0_b420_145330_1hz.avi

faam-video-ffc_faam_20081113_r0_b420_095326_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ffc_faam_20081113_r0_b420_105326_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ffc_faam_20081113_r0_b420_115326_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ffc_faam_20081113_r0_b420_125326_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ffc_faam_20081113_r0_b420_135326_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ffc_faam_20081113_r0_b420_145326_1hz.avi

faam-video-ufc_faam_20081113_r0_b420_095334_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ufc_faam_20081113_r0_b420_105334_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ufc_faam_20081113_r0_b420_115334_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ufc_faam_20081113_r0_b420_125334_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ufc_faam_20081113_r0_b420_135334_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ufc_faam_20081113_r0_b420_145334_1hz.avi

No Digital8 video recordings were made on this flight.